

ENTRUST

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D7.1 Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable outlines the initial planning of the ENTRUST project in terms of Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, and Standardization. It highlights the project's focus on effective communication and dissemination to achieve key performance indicators and maximize impact. The project utilizes various channels, including its website and social media platforms, to disseminate findings and engage stakeholders. Active participation in events and conferences further extends the project's reach and facilitates collaboration opportunities. Standardization is also emphasized to contribute to international cooperation and establish common guidelines in IoT security for healthcare. The project continuously monitors and evaluates its efforts to refine strategies and achieve desired outcomes. Overall, ENTRUST demonstrates a comprehensive and strategic approach to communication, dissemination, exploitation, and standardization, resulting in the advancement of IoT security in healthcare and international collaboration in cybersecurity.</p>		
Keywords	communication, dissemination, standardization, IPR, innovation, exploitation		

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Nature of the deliverable:	R	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet of Things Innovation
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CTA	Call To Action
IoT	Internet of Things
IoTSF	Internet of Things Security Foundation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MDCG	Medical Device Coordination Group
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Description
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
OSD	Open-Source Development
PPT	PowerPoint presentation
SDO	Standard Developing Organization
SEO	Search engine optimization
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the ENTRUST project’s dissemination, communication, standardization, and exploitation plan. It serves as a comprehensive document outlining the tools, channels, and activities to ensure consistent and successful visual and communicative

representation of the project. The deliverable establishes the initial communication roadmap, activities, and tools that will be utilized throughout the project's lifetime, along with exploitation, standardization, and dissemination activities. Furthermore, the document describes the mix of channels, tools, and activities for reaching the ENTRUST target audience and objectives, that includes a combination of synchronous (conferences, clustering with other projects, participation to events, etc.) and asynchronous approaches (newsletters, social media tactics, etc.). The communication strategy of the ENTRUST project aims to raise awareness among the industrial and research community, disseminate innovative project results to various communities of the IoT, organize workshops and interact with related groups, and plan for exploitation. The strategy encompasses standardization efforts, scientific dissemination, and engagement with research, academic, and industrial stakeholders. In the context of the standardization, the project will establish strong relationships with relevant bodies to introduce the project's innovative approach and introduce its outcomes. ENTRUST will take a dual approach to standardization: investigating existing standards and regulations to create a consolidated list for project partners to guide towards implementation, as well as collaborating with Standard Developing Organizations (SDOs) to contribute to their efforts and submit proposals, where relevant. In addition, the deliverable outlines a strategy for successful exploitation of project results, including partners' exploitation plans, and intellectual property rights, aiming to maximize the project's results and ensure long-term benefits for stakeholders. It involves various steps and actions to effectively leverage the project's assets and create value. Key elements include defining the value proposition, identifying stakeholders and market segments, and managing intellectual property. The strategy includes activities like workshops to update assets, identify stakeholders, and develop Intellectual Property (IP) management plans. To ensure the long-term sustainability of the project's results, a robust plan is developed, which may involve partnerships, further funding opportunities, or even establishing a spin-off company. Furthermore, tailored exploitation strategies are created for each partner, considering their strengths and market positions, but also regular impact assessments are conducted to evaluate the success of exploitation activities. Overall, Deliverable D7.1 provides a comprehensive overview of the ENTRUST project's communication, dissemination, standardization, and exploitation mechanisms, roadmap, and strategies. The plans outlined in D7.1 will undergo continuous monitoring and revision throughout the project's duration to ensure maximum impact.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

ENTRUST leads the forefront of digital transformation in the healthcare industry by securing the implementation of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs). The CMDs play a crucial role in revolutionizing healthcare outcomes, cost-saving measures, and patient safety enhancements. However, the proliferation of CMDs also introduces a higher risk of cyber-attacks and data compromises due to the expansion of connectivity interfaces and processing capacity. In response to this challenge, ENTRUST develops a comprehensive approach to mitigate these risks through robust medical device security, strong authentication mechanisms, and trust management protocols. One of the key advancements brought forth by ENTRUST is the introduction of dynamic trust assessment. This ground-breaking feature disrupts the traditional CMD value chain by bolstering cybersecurity measures and bridging existing security gaps. Through dynamic trust assessment, ENTRUST ensures that the trustworthiness and integrity of CMDs are continuously monitored and evaluated, enabling swift identification and mitigation of potential security threats during the runtime.

The ENTRUST project encompasses a well-designed architecture that covers the entire lifecycle of CMDs. From device manufacturing to deployment and ongoing usage, the framework provides a comprehensive security framework that safeguards CMDs against cyber-attacks and data breaches. Real-world use cases further validate the effectiveness of the ENTRUST Framework across a diverse range of devices (from wearables to high-end equipment), ensuring its practical applicability and relevance in different healthcare scenarios. By placing a strong emphasis on medical device security and trust management, ENTRUST not only enables the seamless integration of CMDs into healthcare systems but also instils confidence among healthcare professionals and patients alike. With ENTRUST, the healthcare industry can harness the full potential of Connected Medical Devices, knowing that robust security measures are in place to protect sensitive patient data and critical healthcare infrastructure. In summary, ENTRUST stands as a pioneering force in driving digital transformation in healthcare through the adoption of Connected Medical Devices. By addressing the rising security concerns surrounding CMDs, ENTRUST fortifies the healthcare ecosystem with a state-of-the-art security framework, bolstering patient safety, improving outcomes, and paving the way for a more secure and efficient future in healthcare.

ENTRUST's Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan elaborates on the communication and dissemination strategy. The project recognizes the critical role of effective communication and dissemination in creating awareness, generating stakeholder interest, and ensuring societal impact. The Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan outlines a comprehensive strategy to facilitate these processes and support the success of the project. By providing the ENTRUST consortium with a clear framework, this plan ensures that communication and dissemination activities are aligned with project objectives, monitored through performance indicators, and targeted towards relevant audiences.

The plan encompasses several important components. Firstly, it establishes communication guidelines that outline the principles and best practices to be followed throughout the project. These guidelines ensure consistency and clarity in messaging, reinforcing the project's brand and objectives. Furthermore, the plan identifies the target audiences of ENTRUST, enabling tailored communication approaches to reach different stakeholders effectively. By understanding the needs and interests of these audiences, the project can deliver impactful messages that resonate with their specific contexts. To facilitate effective communication, the plan provides a timeline with defined deadlines for different activities. This ensures a structured approach and allows for proper planning and coordination within the consortium. Additionally, the plan incorporates a review procedure to maintain the quality and relevance of communication materials and outputs. This iterative feedback process guarantees that information shared with stakeholders is accurate, up-to-date, and aligned with project goals.

The visual identity of the project is also addressed within the plan. Establishing a consistent and recognizable visual identity enhances brand recognition and reinforces the project's credibility. Office templates, website structure, and components are detailed to ensure a cohesive and user-friendly online presence. Social media accounts and other digital platforms play a crucial role in modern communication strategies. The plan identifies the social media accounts that will be utilized to engage with target audiences effectively. Leveraging these platforms allows for wider reach, active engagement, and real-time interaction with stakeholders. Also, it includes a "toolkit" with print marketing and promotional materials. This toolkit equips the consortium with ready-to-use resources, such as brochures, posters, and presentations, ensuring consistent and impactful dissemination of project outcomes.

Workshops and potential synergies are emphasized in the plan as valuable opportunities for knowledge exchange, collaboration, and maximizing the project's impact. By actively participating in relevant workshops and seeking synergies with related initiatives, ENTRUST can foster

collaboration, share insights, and amplify the dissemination efforts. The ultimate goal of the dissemination and communication activities outlined in the plan is to enhance the project's societal impact. By ensuring visibility, creating awareness, and supporting the adoption of project results, ENTRUST aims to generate a lasting influence on the healthcare industry and beyond. The plan aligns with the Key Performance Indicators established in the Grant Agreement, which measure the project's outreach of scientific and non-scientific outputs and dissemination to stakeholders.

Importantly, the plan recognizes that dissemination and communication are ongoing activities that require continuous engagement with both internal and external audiences. It outlines three main phases to structure the activities effectively, ensuring a strategic approach throughout the project's duration.

The standardization methodology of the ENTRUST project serves the purpose of ensuring alignment with relevant standards and regulations to achieve the project's vision. It recognizes the importance of standardization for establishing collaborations and introducing the project's innovative approach. The methodology involves a dual approach: firstly, conducting an investigation of existing standards and regulations to compile a comprehensive list for project partners' reference (also in line with T2.1), and secondly, establishing liaisons with relevant Standards Development Organizations (SDOs) to actively contribute and propose improvements to existing standards or bring forward new work items. By engaging with SDOs, ENTRUST aims to influence the development of standards and incorporate its innovative approach, ultimately ensuring compliance and shaping the standards framework accordingly.

ENTRUST's exploitation strategy aims to commercialize its assets and outcomes while ensuring the long-term sustainability of its activities. It combines strategic business planning and marketing analysis to address digital risks in the medical industry and leverage its results to develop innovative solutions. The strategy emphasizes compatibility with Open Science principles and collaboration within the research community. It explores alternative paths for exploitation to identify new opportunities and markets for its solutions. By transitioning research outcomes into market offerings, the strategy aims to maximize the project's impact and provides tangible benefits to stakeholders in the healthcare sector.

In summary, the Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan serves as a comprehensive guide to drive effective communication and dissemination efforts within the ENTRUST project. By establishing clear objectives, target audiences, performance indicators, and utilizing various tools and channels, ENTRUST aims to maximize its impact, foster collaboration, and ensure the widest adoption of its results.

1.2 Document Structure

This document is structured in 8 major chapters and 2 Annexes:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the document, providing an elaboration on the purpose and scope,
- **Chapter 2** outlines the dissemination and communication strategy, emphasizing on the project's target groups, KPIs, initial activities and planning towards the next months,
- **Chapter 3** provides the visual identity of the project and detailed descriptions of each component in the ENTRUST project's dissemination and communication kit,
- **Chapter 4** emphasizes the creation of awareness through dissemination, communication, and outreach activities, with a particular focus on highlighting the sustainable approach,
- **Chapter 5** is dedicated to capacity building and contributions to clusters,
- **Chapter 6** includes the presentation and plans for activities pertaining to standardization, establishment of synergies with similar research initiatives and projects, as well as plans for liaisons and contributions to associations,
- **Chapter 7** presents in detail the exploitation plan,
- **Chapter 8** concludes the deliverable,
- **Chapter 9 - Annex A** includes the ENTRUST Standardization engagement questionnaire,
- **Chapter 10 - Annex B** includes the ENTRUST OSD Plan Template.

2 Dissemination & Communication Strategy

Work Package 7 focuses on identifying relevant stakeholders, preparing promotional materials, and organizing activities to establish an inclusive and engaged ENTRUST community. This deliverable outlines a comprehensive dissemination and communication plan to achieve the aforementioned goals, including target audience identification, knowledge and results dissemination strategy, ENTRUST website architecture, communication methods, tools, and promotional materials. It provides an overview of planned activities and potential liaison opportunities with standardization working groups and other EU project initiatives. Additionally, it defines rules and procedures for implementing, monitoring, and evaluating communication and engagement activities. By utilizing the resources provided in this deliverable, ENTRUST partners have access to the established processes for the effective communication and dissemination of the project results, as well as for their exploitation. Furthermore, deliverable 7.1 lays the foundation for the other two deliverables of work package 7, namely D7.2 Impact Maximization Activities Interim Report and D7.3 Impact Maximization Activities Final Report. These reports will encompass various aspects such as documentation on dissemination, communication, clustering, standardization, and exploitation activities. They will also highlight open-source contributions, workshop organization activities, and provide reports on business models, market analysis, and business planning. The plan will be continuously evaluated and updated throughout the project, with major updates included in periodic reports and subsequent deliverable versions on M15 and M36 of the project

A clear communication and dissemination strategy is essential for the execution of a dissemination and communication plan. Therefore, the ENTRUST project has set out a clear strategy for dissemination and communication activities. The objectives of this strategy is:

- to ensure the efficient communication and dissemination of the project's developments and results through various means.
- to develop a clear and distinct identity for ENTRUST project and utilize it consistently to enhance the project's visibility among the target groups.
- to cultivate ENTRUST awareness status among technical target audiences by describing its benefits through appropriate messages and maximising its outreach.
- to promote a European collaborative approach to research and innovation by establishing and managing of liaisons and synergies with relevant projects and initiatives.
- to secure a certain level of impact among the target groups.

These objectives will facilitate the exploitation of ENTRUST's outcomes and will ensure the overall sustainability of the project.

Figure 1 - Dissemination & Communication Phases

The initial phase, called "Engage," involves establishing the ENTRUST branding and corporate identity, creating the project website, and developing standard templates for project documents and presentations. During the second phase (Promote), consortium partners will focus on producing scientific papers for conferences and journals to discuss the project's scientific findings. This phase includes presentations at conferences and workshops to increase awareness among scientific and industrial stakeholders, foster discussions, gather feedback, and contribute to the project's success. Scientific publications and select public deliverables will be shared on the project website, while social media platforms like Twitter, LinkedIn, and a project blog will be regularly updated to engage a broader audience. Newsletters, posters, workshop information, conference participation, videos, interviews, and other means of communication will be utilized to encourage interactive communication within and outside the consortium. Press releases and newsletters will be published for significant milestones and specific project events. The third phase (Exploit) involves utilizing dissemination activities for exploitation purposes, such as commercial use or public policymaking. Ongoing dissemination efforts will continue even after the project concludes to promote the results and attract the target audience.

To address the abovementioned objectives of the dissemination and communication strategy, we established several key principles, including personalized and multi-channel communication targeted towards specific target groups, active participation in events to share ENTRUST's achievements and attract the target groups, and the cultivation of long-term relationships with stakeholders. While talking about communication activities, the goal is to highlight the benefits of the ENTRUST project for society, e.g. by showing the public society and media the impact of our project on everyday lives. When it comes to dissemination activities the goal is to transfer knowledge and make project results available to an audience that may take an interest. Specific activities, such as developing communication materials like logos and style formats for brochures, and maintaining an updated project website, are essential components of the strategy. It is important to emphasize the complementary nature of these elements and activities, minimizing overlaps and ensuring the effectiveness of communication and dissemination within the objectives of ENTRUST.

YEAR 1 - 2023			
Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Project Announcement Letter	2 Blog posts	3 Blog posts	Workshop @ GloTS 2023
Project Branding	1st project newsletter	Meeting under the HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-1 3-01 initiative	3 Blog posts
Project website & Social Media	Deliverable 7.1	IWAPS 2023 - International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions	2nd project newsletter
Project Templates	ERATOSTHENES Project Workshop: "Trust and Identity Management for IoT"		Policy Brief/White paper with Recommendations about MDCG-2019-16 guidance revisions
Reporting excel file	PUZZLE INTERNATIONAL CYBERSECURITY CONFERENCE		
YEAR 2 - 2024			
Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Workshop "ENTRUST architecture and preliminary recommendations about MDCG 2019-16 revisions"	3rd project Newsletter		Workshop "Post-market surveillance and runtime verification of medical devices trustworthiness"
			4th project Newsletter
YEAR 3 - 2025			
Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Workshop "Continuous conformity assessment and certification based on runtime verifiable evidence"	Workshop "ENTRUST Customizable Trusted Computing Base enhancing PUFs and TEEs"	On-site pilot demonstration in Romania	6th Project Newsletter
	5th project Newsletter		ENTRUST Day Trainings

Figure 2 - Dissemination & Communication Strategy Timeline

The success of the dissemination and communication strategy depends on its ability to effectively reach target groups through a diverse range of channels, which forms the foundation for attracting partners, advancing state-of-the-art knowledge and technologies, and making positive societal contributions in line with the goals of the European Union.

2.1 ENTRUST Target Groups

ENTRUST, being an IoT and health-focused project, has taken careful measures to ensure the effective implementation of its communication and dissemination plan. As part of this effort, a thorough identification and selection process has been undertaken to determine the project's target audience. The following are the key segments that ENTRUST aims to engage with:

- **Healthcare providers and organizations:** Healthcare providers and organizations, such as hospitals, clinics, and nursing homes, encounter various security challenges when integrating multiple connected medical devices from different manufacturers. It is crucial for these devices to seamlessly work together within clinical workflows without compromising the overall security of their operations. ENTRUST addresses these issues by establishing security visibility across complex networks. The solution is specifically designed to meet the requirements of this target group, considering the lack of experienced and well-trained personnel in cybersecurity. ENTRUST offers easy-to-deploy methodologies and explainable features to ensure smooth implementation and understanding.
- **Device Manufacturers:** Device manufacturers prioritize the design of their devices and aim to maintain control over their composition and performance throughout their lifespan. ENTRUST recognizes this focus and offers a secure-by-design methodology along with a set of foundational cybersecurity elements. These components contribute to continuous security verification of the device, ensuring effective post-market surveillance of connected medical devices. By following a security-by-design approach, manufacturers can demonstrate compliance with guidelines such as MDCG 2019-16 or other applicable standards. This includes adhering to rigorous quality standards during manufacturing and ensuring the device functions as intended. The same commitment to quality applies to the entire product lifecycle. Additionally, as many devices are complex systems with multiple components and accessories, ENTRUST addresses the manufacturers' need for real-time authentication of these components during deployment.
- **Suppliers:** Medical device suppliers will have access to reliable information through the enhanced certificates of conformity. This establishes a trusted relationship and increases confidence between suppliers and manufacturers, while also providing the end customers

with the necessary evidence of the trustworthiness and data integrity of the connected medical device. ENTRUST ensures the integrity of data and the accurate delivery of medical information through cryptographically verified formal models and a remote attestation mechanism. Additionally, the secure lifecycle procedures, security policies, and real-time Conformity Certificates facilitate seamless collaboration among all stakeholders in the value chain.

- **Healthcare Professionals and Administrators:** This includes doctors, nurses, clinicians, and other healthcare providers who directly interact with patients. They play a crucial role in the adoption and utilization of CMDs and can benefit from the benefits offered by ENTRUST. Targeted communication can focus on the improved patient outcomes, cost savings, and enhanced patient safety that CMDs can bring. Also, this audience includes hospital administrators, healthcare executives, and policymakers responsible for making decisions regarding the implementation and integration of CMDs into healthcare systems. Communication efforts can highlight the potential efficiency gains and operational improvements, that the ENTRUST framework can offer, thereby influencing their decision-making process.
- **National & EU Public Authorities, Policy / Decision Makers:** The increasing complexity of information systems is giving rise to new cybersecurity challenges and vulnerabilities. Trust and security are at the forefront of the EU Digital Single Market strategy, and combating cybercrime is a top priority on the EU Security Agenda. Additionally, governments and EU regulators are imposing strict requirements regarding the protection of personal data. In light of these factors, ENTRUST has set an ambitious goal of addressing existing cybersecurity concerns through the implementation of a real-time certification approach under an EU-label certification. This approach enables EU vendors and providers to foster innovation and enhance their competitiveness in the Digital Single Market, while also bolstering EU autonomy in cybersecurity and promoting self-sustainability in European businesses.
- **Patients / General public:** With the safety and privacy of patients in mind, ENTRUST specifically addresses the unique requirements of medical devices that differentiate them from conventional IoT systems. These requirements include safety, reliability, and resilience, which aim to protect patients from any unacceptable risks, physical harm, or damage to their health caused directly or indirectly by cybersecurity incidents. By incorporating enhanced security features, ENTRUST not only improves public acceptance but also reduces any concerns related to the use of connected medical devices. The

features of ENTRUST ensure privacy through the use of zero-knowledge techniques and promote resilience by maintaining an acceptable level of service and implementing self-recovery capabilities in the face of disruptions. Additionally, ENTRUST emphasizes reliability by upholding expected performance, availability, and accuracy under specified conditions for a defined period of time through the enforcement of trusted policies and automated updates.

- **Cybersecurity & Trusted Computing researchers / engineers, IoT Community:** The scientific area of ENTRUST project is emerging, thus more and more researchers and engineers will be encouraged to focus on it. One of the objectives of the project is to support Open Science and contribute to the vast IoT community in general, showcasing its work and results.

In the same pathways, understanding the characteristics and roles of internal and external stakeholders, as well as their interactions and needs, is vital for successful communication and information sharing. By identifying the target audiences and their preferences, the most effective channels and tools can be utilized to deliver key messages. Various methods such as publications, exhibitions, conferences/workshops/seminars, press releases, and promotional materials are employed for information dissemination. Additionally, establishing a strong online presence and leveraging the networks of consortium members is crucial for maximizing the strategy's reach across multiple touchpoints.

Table 1 - Target groups & Activities

Target Groups	Activities	Key Messages
<p>Healthcare providers and organizations</p>	<p>Announcement Letter, Project website, Social Media, Newsletters, Blog Posts, Brochures, Conferences, Pilot Demonstrations, Trainings, Webinars, ENTRUST Day</p>	<p>Entrust solution offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced Security • Seamless Integration • User-Friendly Implementation • Explainable Features • Tailored to Healthcare
<p>Device Manufacturers</p>	<p>Announcement Letter, Project website, Social Media, Newsletters, Blog Posts, Brochures, Conferences, Pilot Demonstrations, Trainings, Webinars, ENTRUST Day</p>	<p>Entrust solution offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure-by-Design Methodology. • Post-Market Surveillance • Compliance and Quality Standards • End-to-End Product Lifecycle

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthened Authentication
Suppliers	Announcement Letter, Project website, Social Media, Newsletters, Blog Posts, Brochures, Non-scientific Publications, Pilot Demonstrations, Trainings, Webinars, ENTRUST Day	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entrust solution offers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reliable Information Evidence of Trustworthiness Data Integrity and Accurate Delivery Secure Collaboration
Healthcare Professionals and Administrators	Announcement Letter, Project website, Social Media, Newsletters, Blog Posts, Brochures, Conferences, Pilot Demonstrations, Trainings, Webinars, ENTRUST Day	<p>Entrust solution offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced Security Seamless Integration User-Friendly Implementation Explainable Features Tailored to Healthcare
National & EU Public Authorities, Policy / Decision Makers	Announcement Letter, Project website, Social Media, Newsletters, Blog Posts, Videos, Brochures, Conferences, Trainings, Webinars, ENTRUST Day	<p>Entrust solution offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addressing Cybersecurity Challenges EU Digital Single Market Strategy Combating Cybercrime EU Autonomy in Cybersecurity Promoting Self-Sustainability
Patients / General public	Announcement Letter, Project website, Social Media, Newsletters, Blog Posts, Videos, Brochures, Non-scientific Publications, Trainings, Webinars, ENTRUST Day	<p>Entrust solution offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient Safety and Privacy Enhanced Security Privacy Protection Resilience and Self-Recovery Reliability and Trusted Policies
Cybersecurity & Trusted Computing researchers / engineers, IoT Community	Announcement Letter, Project website, Social Media, Newsletters, Blog Posts, Brochures, Scientific Papers, conferences, Trainings, Webinars, ENTRUST Day	<p>Entrust solution offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emerging Scientific Area Support for Open Science Contribution to IoT Community Research and Development Opportunities Collaboration and Knowledge Exchange

2.2 Dissemination & Communication KPIs

The Dissemination plan of ENTRUST, being a crucial aspect of the project, is carefully monitored through a range of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs have been established to effectively track the progress and impact of the dissemination activities. The plan is structured into three distinct phases, namely, Awareness Creation, Continuity of Information Flow, and Result Orientation, each designed to gauge stakeholder engagement in different ways. To ensure accurate measurement and evaluation, specific KPIs are assigned to each type of activity based on the target group of stakeholders. These KPIs are tailored to align with the goals and objectives of the dissemination plan, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of engagement and impact across various stakeholder segments.

By closely monitoring these KPIs, ENTRUST can assess the effectiveness of its dissemination efforts, identify areas for improvement, and make informed decisions regarding communication strategies. This data-driven approach ensures that the project remains on track in terms of engaging stakeholders and achieving the desired outcomes. Through the systematic tracking of KPIs throughout the dissemination plan's different phases, ENTRUST can gather valuable insights into the level of awareness generated, the continuity of information flow, and the extent to which stakeholders are embracing and utilizing the project's results. This information serves as a foundation for refining communication strategies, maximizing stakeholder engagement, and ultimately driving the project's overall success. By continuously monitoring and analysing the KPIs, ENTRUST can make data-informed adjustments to its dissemination activities, ensuring that the right messages are reaching the right stakeholders at the right time. This iterative approach helps to optimize the impact and effectiveness of the dissemination plan, fostering strong stakeholder engagement and maximizing the project's overall reach and influence.

In summary, the Dissemination plan of ENTRUST incorporates a range of KPIs to measure the effectiveness of its dissemination efforts. Through the careful selection and tracking of these KPIs across the plan's distinct phases, ENTRUST can assess stakeholder engagement, identify areas for improvement, and make informed decisions to enhance the project's impact and success.

Table 2 - Awareness creation

Type of Activity	Target Groups	KPIs	Means of completion
Announcement letter	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, Policy / Decision Makers, General public, Research community	> 5000 people	Posts on social media, on project website and on partner's websites/ social media

Project website and branding	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, Policy / Decision Makers, General public, Research community	> 1000 unique visitors, > 200 registrants, > 350 blog interactions	Posts on social media, on project website and on partner's websites/ social media. Marketing pack and promotional press kit (Rollup, brochure, banner)
Audio and Video Material	Policy / Decision Makers, General public	1 Promo + 1/Pilot + 1 Impact + 2-4 interviews or podcast episodes	Audio and Visual engagement via videos/ interviews/ podcasts to enable-Source Impl. Roadmap
Social Media	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, Policy / Decision Makers, General public, Research community	> 1000 followers, > 800 posts, > 5000 interactions	Posts on social media and on project website about the synergies, project activities and results

Table 3 - Continuity of information flow

Type of Activity	Target Groups	KPIs	Means of completion
Press release, blog posts, articles, whitepapers	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, Policy / Decision Makers, General public, Research community	> 4/per year (> 1000 people)	Distribution via social media and project website
Participation in and publication of scientific papers in conferences and high impact factor journals	Research community	> 4 Journal articles > 15 Conference papers	Participation to conferences (IEEE EuroS&P, ACM WiSec, NDSS, ACM CCS, IEEE DCOSS, ESORICS, Asia CCS, IEEE INFOCOM, IEEE WF-IoT, ARES Conference) and journals (IEEE TIFS, IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, ACM TOPS, IEEE TDSC)

Interaction with policy makers	Policy / Decision Makers	> 6 synergies established with policy makers	Synergies (via e-mail or physically)
Digital liaisons with related projects	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, Policy / Decision Makers, General public, Research community	Workshops organized (3) + attended (> 5), > 500 visitors, 10 speakers; 5 posts in CORDIS/other EC systems; 10 project synergies (incl. common product/services by joining project assets)	Feedback exchanged with national, European, and international research projects from the same field through e-mails, social media and face-to-face meetings
Non-scientific Publications	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, General public	> 5 Industry Magazines, > 6 Industrial Automotive Cyber Security Conferences (e.g., InfoSec EU, IAHS), 1 exhibition, 2 demonstration days	Training/ Showcases, Open access exhibitions and demonstration events that present the use cases and results in a lightweight manner.
Standardization associations	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, Policy / Decision Makers, Research community	(EU & International) Automotive > 3, Transport/Mobility > 3, Standards Orgs > 4	Interactions with standardization WGs and committees for pushing the core artefacts of ENTRUST related to Security & Trusted Computing, Trust Assessment, Guidance on Cybersecurity for Medical Devices, Data Sharing, Conformity Checking, Runtime Verification, etc. Meeting attendance and common publications

Table 4 - Result orientation

Type of Activity	Target Groups	KPIs	Means of completion
On-site Pilot Demonstrations/ Workshops	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers	> 1 demonstration per pilot, > 2 workshops per pilot, > 30 attendees each	Workshops, Short videos and (social) media coverage
Online and/or F2F Training/Webinar	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, Policy / Decision Makers, General public, Research community	2 webinar/trainings, > 50 attendees	Training activities (webinars)
ENTRUST Day	Healthcare providers, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers, Policy / Decision Makers, General public, Research community	> 80-100 participants	Present the project results and future work in a F2F workshop or webinar

The following KPIs will be monitored during the whole lifetime of the project with the use of monitor excel sheets stored in project’s repository, where the consortium will keep track of the activities and results of the communication and dissemination plan.

No.	Partner's Name	Type of Action	Notes	Date	Audience	Email (Contact Person)	Link	Impact
1	SINTEF	Journal Article	Suggestion					
2	SINTEF	Journal Article	Suggestion					
3	SINTEF	Journal Article	Suggestion					
4	SINTEF	Journal Article	Suggestion					
5	SINTEF	Conference Paper	Consortium Aware Digital Teams to Support Software Management at the Edge	27-28 May 2023	Conference Audience			Core 8 conference

Figure 3 - KPIs Monitoring Excel Sheets

2.2.1 Initial Activities due to M6

Despite the fact that the ENTRUST Project has been recently launched, several communication and dissemination actions have been already carried out. Indicatively, the 6-month period initial activities (M1-M6) are reported in the following Table 6. For the website and social media channels also the corresponding 6-month metrics and KPIs are provided.

Table 5 - Initial Activities

Type of Activity	KPIs	Reached so far
Announcement letter	> 5000 people	5112 people (Totally from the project's website/ social media & partners' website/ social media)
Project website and branding	> 1000 unique visitors, > 200 registrants, > 350 blog interactions	226 unique visitors, 33 registrants, 96 blog interactions
Social Media	> 1000 followers, > 800 posts, > 5000 interactions	146 followers, 58 posts, 589 interactions (Totally on LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube)

Digital liaisons with related projects	10 project synergies Workshops organized (3) attended (> 5) > 500 visitors 10 speakers 5 posts in CORDIS/other EC systems;	4 project synergies (<u>CERTIFY, MEMECYS, PUZZLE, CROSSCON</u>) 2 Workshops attended 250 visitors 2 speakers
Press release, blog posts, articles, whitepapers	> 4/per year (> 1000 people)	2 blog posts 3 News items 96 people 1 st project newsletter

Additionally, the ENTRUST Project has already participated in a few events/workshops (Table 6), that share the same research scientific area. In these events partners of the consortium presented a high-level overview of the project, highlighting its objectives and the expected results, but also exchanged knowledge with other projects' consortiums.

Table 6 - Events/ Workshops so far

Event / Workshop	Partner	Date	Attendance
HaDEA meeting	UNIS/UBI	23 March 2023	n/a
ERATOSTHENES Project Workshop: "Trust and Identity Management for IoT"	UBI	16 June 2023	~70 people
PUZZLE INTERNATIONAL	UBI	21 June 2023	~ 100 people

CYBERSECURITY CONFERENCE			
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(Please note that since the editing of this deliverable was finalized in June 2023 (M6), it was not feasible to include all the latest activities).

2.2.2 Planning towards the upcoming months

The ENTRUST consortium is committed to maintaining an active presence in the coming months and has proactively planned a series of events, workshops, and communication activities to further promote the project's mission and showcase its progress. These initiatives are designed to seize additional communication and dissemination opportunities as they arise. While the list is non-exhaustive, it provides a glimpse of the upcoming events and activities planned by the consortium, as summarized in Table 7:

Table 7 - Upcoming Activities / Events / Workshops

Activities / Event / Workshop	Partner(s)	Date
Meeting under the HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13-01 initiative	UBI	July 2023
INCOGNITO & SECONDO Summer School: Innovation in Attribute-based Authentication & Negotiation Skills for Research Projects and Project Management in Cybersecurity	UPRC	July 2023

GloTS (Global IoT Summit) – 5th Workshop on Internet of Things Security and Privacy	UMU, UPRC	October 2023
IWAPS 2023 - International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions	UPRC	August 2023
PQCrypto 2023 The 14th International Conference on Post-Quantum Cryptography College Park, MD, USA	SURREY	August 2023
ASE 2023	SINTEF	September 2023
9th IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things (IEEE WFIoT2023)	UMU	October 2023
ISSRE 2023	SINTEF	October 2023
MODELS 2023	SINTEF	October 2023
ESEC/FSE 2023	SINTEF	December 2023
ISSRE 2024	SINTEF	Q4 2024
MODELS 2024	SINTEF	Q4 2024
ESEC/FSE 2024	SINTEF	Q4 2024
2nd project Newsletter	FN, UPRC	Q4 2023
Policy Brief/White paper with Recommendations about MDCG-2019-16 guidance revisions	UBI	Q4 2023
Workshop "ENTRUST architecture and preliminary recommendations about MDCG 2019-16 revisions"	UNIS	Q1 2024

3rd project Newsletter	FN, UPRC	Q2 2024
Workshop "Post-market surveillance and runtime verification of medical devices trustworthiness"	UBI	Q4 2024
Workshop "Continuous conformity assessment and certification based on runtime verifiable evidence"	UMU	Q1 2025
Workshop "ENTRUST Customizable Trusted Computing Base enhancing PUFs and TEEs"	QUBI	Q2 2025
5th project Newsletter	FN, UPRC	Q2 2025
On-site pilot demonstration in Romania	POLARIS	Q3 2025
6th Project Newsletter	FN, UPRC	Q4 2025
ENTRUST Day	ALL	Q4 2025
Trainings	ALL	Q4 2025
EHiN 2023 (largest e-health conference in Norway)	TLU	Q4 2023
EHiN 2024 (largest e-health conference in Norway)	TLU	Q4 2024
Vitalis (largest e-health conference in the Nordics)	TLU	Q2 2024
EMVTE (e-health conference in Stockholm)	TLU	Q1 2024
Norway Health Tech (Norwegian cluster for e-health and med-tech companies, Tellu is member)	TLU	Q1 2024
SmartCare center cluster (Norwegian cluster for e-health and med-tech companies, Tellu is member)	TLU	Q1 2024

3 Dissemination & Communication Kit

This chapter describes the ENTRUST overall communication kit, which includes the project website as the major communication tool, as well as all communication and dissemination materials used within the project. All these materials are freely accessible for download on the project website. Additional materials, which will be created throughout the duration of the project, will be added in D7.3 “Impact Maximization Activities Final Report”.

In general, we grant open access to all communication and dissemination materials. If, in a certain case, other license requirements must be taken into consideration, this will be marked accordingly. All the project material will be marked with the following sentence: “Funded by European Commission under Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement No. 101095634). Views and opinions expressed are those of the ENTRUST consortium authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or its delegated Agency DG HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.1 Visual Identity of the Project

The ENTRUST brand identity is the tangible expression of what we stand for. ENTRUST is an EU project funded by the #HorizonEurope programme, that aims to provide an end-to-end trust management system for medical devices.

We selected specific colours for our logo to convey key messages and evoke certain emotions. The use of red in our logo represents health and medical devices, as it is commonly associated with vitality and energy. Blue was chosen to install a sense of security and trust, as it is often linked to reliability and calmness. The incorporation of purple, created by blending red and blue, symbolizes innovation and creativity, reflecting our commitment to advancement in the industry. Finally, the inclusion of neutral colours such as greys and black and white provides a balanced and versatile foundation, ensuring our logo remains timeless and adaptable in various contexts.

Table 8 - Logo colours

Hex #ae2c5c

C 27
M 96
Y 46
K 8

R 174
G 44
B 92

Hex #13b1d8

C 72
M 9
Y 9
K 0

R 19
G 177
B 216

Hex #0D89A8

C 83
M 33
Y 25
K 1

R 13
G 137

Hex #71618c

C 63
M 67
Y 23
K 4

R 113
G 97

Hex #353535

C 69
M 63
Y 62
K 57

R 53
G 53

B 168

B 140

B 53

Hex #000000

Hex #F2F2F2

C 0
M 0
Y 0
K 100

C 4
M 3
Y 3
K 0

R 0
G 0
B 0

R 242
G 242
B 242

For the typography we are proposing two different typefaces one for office templates and one for online use (website).

The proposed typeface for Microsoft Office templates is Montserrat. A geometric sans-serif typeface designed by Argentine graphic designer Julieta Ulanovsky and released in 2011. It was inspired by posters, signs and painted windows from the first half of the twentieth century, seen in the historic Montserrat neighbourhood of Buenos Aires. It is available for download: www.fonts.google.com/specimen/Montserrat.

The proposed typeface for online use (website) is Open Sans. A clean and modern sans-serif typeface designed by Steve Matteson and commissioned by Google. It is especially designed for legibility across print, web, and mobile interfaces. Open Sans is excellent for any type of use. It's

incredibly readable in small sizes and also works great when printed in huge letters. The best thing of all, it's a free font! You are free to use and download it for your next design project. It is available for download: www.fonts.google.com/specimen/Open+Sans.

3.1.1 Project Logo

Table 9 - Project Logo

White version

Symbol/icon for social media, favicon and other applications - version on white

Symbol/icon for social media, favicon and other applications - version on dark

Exclusion zone (clear space)

The logo's and icon's exclusion zones are equal to the height of the wordmark's letter U

Minimum print size

Minimum digital size

Incorrect use

Always protect the integrity and appearance of our logotype. No modification or reinterpretation of the logo should occur as per the illustrated examples.

3.1.2 Project Templates

During the first two (2) months, the project has designed three (3) document templates, which are available to all partners of the consortium. The document template set includes the following items:

- Template for deliverables (Word file),
- Template for presentations (PPT file) and
- Template for documents (memo Word file).

The templates are part of the branding package of the project aiming to ensure standardizing the project documentation with unique visual identity and that all partners should use these templates throughout the project's lifetime.

Figure 4 - Template for Deliverables

Figure 5 - Template for Presentations

Figure 6 - Template for Documents (memo)

3.2 ENTRUST Project Website

The project's website is ENTRUST to a domain and live at [<https://www.entrust-he.eu/>] The content of the website is to be reviewed, approved, and updated by all consortium members until the end of the project. It will include all the news about the activities of ENTRUST and related events that ENTRUST and its consortium members participate in. Consortium members participating in the above will provide the content (text and visual material like photographs, videos, diagrams, infographics etc.) to be uploaded on the website. Papers and other publications related to the project will be uploaded on the website, as well as newsletters, press releases. The website will be kept live for at least 3 years after the project ends.

Figure 7 - Website Homepage

The website structure will be as follows:

1. **Structure:** The website is divided into nine menu sections including: **Home, About, Use cases, Partners (Synergies included), Library (including news, newsletters, blog articles, press releases, downloads), and Contact.**
1. **Home:** This is the main page of the website, which provides information regarding the project, its partners and options that trigger the attention of the end user prompting them to scrutinise and learn more about ENTRUST. The homepage hosts several sections that easily navigate the visitors to the rest pages of the website for additional information.
2. **About:** The “About” page incorporates an overview of the project, its main objectives and missions.
3. **Use Cases:** The use cases section on the project’s website provides a comprehensive overview of the use cases of the project.
4. **Partners:** The ENTRUST partners are proudly presented within the specific page along with their corresponding country of their origin and their specific role in the project. Moreover potential synergies with other relevant projects are elaborated here.
5. **Library:** This section is regularly updated with content including project events, activities, news related to upcoming & past events where partners participated, newsletters, and other impactful dissemination material upon being published. The “News” page offers a preview of ENTRUST published news where visitors can scroll and click on a selected published article and be redirected to the respective page where the full article is made available. In this section there is also all the press releases and finally the brochure (project factsheet) of the project. This section also contains the blog posts.

6. **Contact:** The contact form is an integral part of the website and serves as a bidirectional means of interaction among the stakeholders of the project and the project team. In this section emerging issues and queries are explicated and, upon receipt, they are addressed accordingly by the ENTRUST administration team. Furthermore, clickable icons of the ENTRUST social media channels exist at the header and the footer of the home page through which users can easily visit the respective channels.

Each page of the ENTRUST website includes at the bottom, the disclaimer, the privacy policy, the email of the coordinator, buttons for the social media channels, and the “subscribe to our newsletter” form.

Strategies to increase traffic:

- **Comprehensive Keyword Research:** Extensive research has been conducted to identify relevant keywords and phrases that our target audience frequently searches for. We have carefully selected high-ranking and low-competition keywords to optimize our website's content.
- **On-Page Optimization:** Our web pages have been meticulously optimized by incorporating target keywords in page titles, headings, and content. The content is well-structured, engaging, and tailored to meet the needs of our audience.
- **Valuable and Informative Content:** We consistently produce high-quality, informative, and unique content that aligns with our target keywords. Our website is regularly updated with fresh content to attract search engine crawlers and provide visitors with valuable information.
- **Optimized Website Performance:** We have improved our website's performance by optimizing page load speed, ensuring mobile responsiveness, and enhancing navigation. Our user-friendly website is designed to provide a seamless browsing experience.
- **High-Quality Backlinks:** We have successfully built strong relationships with reputable websites in our industry, earning high-quality backlinks. These backlinks from authoritative sources significantly contribute to our website's credibility and relevance.
- **Effective Social Media Promotion:** Our website content is strategically shared across various social media platforms, resulting in increased visibility and user engagement. By actively engaging with our audience and encouraging content sharing, we have successfully generated more traffic.

- Data-Driven Analysis and Refinement: We regularly analyse website traffic using tools like Google Analytics to identify patterns, trends, and areas for improvement. By leveraging data-driven insights, we continuously refine our SEO strategies to ensure optimal results.

More information and details about the ENTRUST Project website are presented in the corresponding document of Deliverable 7.4.

3.3 ENTRUST Announcement Letter

During the first two (2) weeks of the project, the announcement letter was released to the public, aiming to inform and intrigue mainly the research community and potential stakeholders from industry. The announcement letter is published on the project’s official website and was circulated among the consortium for the partners to share it through their communication channels, such as websites and social media accounts. The main purpose of this letter is to state the beginning of the project’s journey towards its objectives.

In the following figure, the indicative text of the announcement letter is presented.

Indicative title:

<partner name> participates in the ENTRUST Research and Innovation Action on secure connected medical devices.

<partner name> participates in the ENTRUST Research and Innovation Action, officially started on January 1st, 2023. The project is funded by European Commission under Horizon Europe Programme (Grant Agreement No. 101095634), and spans on the period January 2023 – December 2025.

ENTRUST envisions to holistically manage the lifecycle of connected medical devices, strengthening trust in the entire medical ecosystem. The project will leverage a series of breakthrough solutions to enhance assurance without limiting the applicability of connected medical devices. This includes formally verified trust models, remote attestation mechanisms, risk assessment processes, secure lifecycle procedures, security policies, technical recommendations, and real-time conformity certificates based on distributed ledgers. The project will introduce a novel remote attestation mechanism to ensure the device’s correct operation at runtime regardless of its computational power, which will be accompanied by dynamic trust assessment models capable of identifying the required level of trustworthiness per device and service. This will also enable us to define appropriate Protection profiles per device, including targets of validation properties to be attested during runtime. |

The added value and effectiveness of ENTRUST will be validated and evaluated in four real-world use cases ranging from wearable and medical devices used for remote patient monitoring to high-end stationary equipment used in hospitals and clinics.

Within ENTRUST, **<partner name>** undertakes ... **[add a small paragraph describing your role in the project]**.

For more information and updates connect to the project at LinkedIn or Twitter.

Figure 8 - Template of Announcement Letter

3.4 ENTRUST Brochure

The brochure is an informative and visually appealing. Highlights the ENTRUST project's vision, main goals, key technological aspects, and background information. The brochure can be distributed at conferences or other dissemination events to increase the visibility of the ENTRUST project. The project brochure specifically covers the following aspects:

1. Project details, including duration, funding and project number
2. Project vision
3. Project main goals
4. Consortium members and their respective countries
5. Contact details for the project.

Figure 9 - ENTRUST Brochure

3.5 ENTRUST Videos

An official ENTRUST project YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCLIELYnaBbZAowYaZ_98I2g) has been created during the first two (2) months of the project, where all public video material will be uploaded. In general, the context of such videos will be determined by the consortium throughout the project’s lifetime, but the main usage of this dissemination method is to visually showcase the main objectives and the pilots of the project. Furthermore, videos for training purposes will be uploaded towards ENTRUST’s Open-Source Roadmap for CMD Training Reference Implementation.

Figure 10 - YouTube Channel

3.6 ENTRUST Social Media

One of the most important pillars of ENTRUST’s communication is the social media channels. Through the project’s presence in social media channels, the consortium will achieve the objective of the wider exposure of the project’s impact. The selected social media channels are LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/90539253/>) and Twitter (https://twitter.com/EnTrust_Horizon/), along with the abovementioned YouTube channel (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCLIELYnaBbZAowYaZ_98I2g).

Figure 11 - LinkedIn Page

Figure 12 - Twitter Page

A short but important list of advantages and benefits of project’s social media is the following one:

- gaining brand recognition,
- circulating news, activities, and results of the project,
- engaging a wide range of audience among various areas of interest related to cybersecurity and IoT,
- monitoring project’s impact and
- last but not least making synergies and beneficial collaborations with other projects with similar activities and communities.

In this context and to achieve the project’s objectives and KPIs, we have also created some hashtags as identifiers, aiming to boost the audience’s engagement and highlight the uniqueness and significance of the project’s brand:

- #entrust_he
- #meet_entrust

Furthermore, there has been also created a Zenodo Community (https://zenodo.org/communities/entrust_he/), in order to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts related to the project.

Figure 13 - Zenodo Community

3.7 ENTRUST Newsletter

Since email marketing has been recognized as one of the most usable and preferred ways of digital marketing, newsletter is also included in the communication strategy of ENTRUST project.

In general, newsletters are being used to increase the engagement of the public and raise awareness of a topic, while sharing valuable information. Thus, in the context of ENTRUST, the newsletter will be used at regular times, aiming to boost the project's brand and keep the interested audience informed of any updates, enhancing the networking.

The context of the ENTRUST newsletters will be blog posts written by the partners, news, and updates regarding the progress of the project, the project's participation in upcoming events and several interesting external news related to the project's philosophy.

The newsletter sign-up is available via the homepage of ENTRUST's official website, and its operation is being shared through the social media channels in regular project updates.

3.8 ENTRUST Events and Workshops

Awareness, interaction, and promotion of ENTRUST are expected to be positively impacted by the project's representation in relevant events. Events and workshops play a significant role in enabling the consortium to communicate and disseminate the objectives, developments and results of ENTRUST. In the dissemination plan, we have a robust agenda to organize minimum three workshops with other relevant projects we have synergies with. Moreover, we aim to actively participate in more than five workshops to extend our reach and engage with relevant communities. We will organize "ENTRUST Day," the project's final event, where stakeholders from the healthcare industry and research community will be invited. The primary objective of this event is to present the project's results and future work. Distinguished speakers working on related topics will also be invited to enrich the discussions and knowledge exchange. Additionally, we will organize a minimum of two online training sessions during the project. These training activities aim to bridge the gap between practitioners and theoreticians by offering structured and regular training events involving both internal and external members of the project. The goal is to enhance collaboration and knowledge sharing within the ENTRUST project.

According to Table 7, the ENTRUST project has outlined its objectives to include organizing four workshops and conducting various events. These activities aim to address specific topics related to medical device regulation and enhance trustworthiness. **The workshops and events are scheduled as follows:**

- The first workshop, titled "ENTRUST Architecture and Preliminary Recommendations about MDCG 2019-16 Revisions," will be led by UNIS and will take place during the first three months of 2024.
- The second workshop, led by UBI, will focus on "Post-market Surveillance and Runtime Verification of Medical Devices Trustworthiness." This workshop is scheduled for the fourth quarter of 2024.

- UMU will lead the third workshop, which will explore the topic of "Continuous Conformity Assessment and Certification Based on Runtime Verifiable Evidence. The workshop will take place during the first quarter of 2025.
- The fourth workshop, titled "ENTRUST Customizable Trusted Computing Base Enhancing PUFs and TEEs," will be led by QUBI and is planned for the second quarter of 2025.

Additionally, the project partners will facilitate an on-site pilot demonstration in Romania. This demonstration will provide practical insights into the implementation of the ENTRUST project. Furthermore, a final conference/event called the "ENTRUST Day" will be organized, which will offer hands-on trainings and serve as a platform for sharing knowledge and experiences.

These events and workshops are part of our planned agenda and aim to contribute to the advancement of knowledge and solutions in the respective fields. The organizing partners will collaborate with the Dissemination and Communication Officer and the Project Coordinator to refine their plans and initiate preparations for the events. This involves defining the main topic(s), identifying key participants and target audiences, developing a scientific program and agenda, creating promotional material and selecting communication channels, establishing a time schedule, addressing logistics and practical matters, as well as organizing documentation and reporting.

3.9 ENTRUST Scientific and Non – Scientific Publications

The ENTRUST project leverages the expertise and experience of its consortium members to deliver top-notch scientific publications, articles, and whitepapers. ENTRUST will count on an array of tools and channels to disseminate its findings and technological developments. Both scientific and non-scientific articles will be utilized to ensure wide dissemination of the project's results. The project aims to publish special issues in scientific journals, inviting contributions from experts and researchers from the consortium to present the project as a valuable pool of knowledge. By promoting and raising awareness of the innovations and breakthroughs made in the field of connected medical devices, ENTRUST advances its mission.

ENTRUST will disseminate the results of the project in accordance with Article 17 in ANNEX 5 of the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement.

The following actions will be taken to ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to the results:

- Beneficiaries will deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version, or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication into a trusted repository for scientific publications at the latest when it is published.
- Immediate open access will be provided to the deposited publication through the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or an equivalent license. For monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g., CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND).
- Information about any research output or necessary tools and instruments to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication will be provided via the repository.
- Beneficiaries or authors will retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

In addition, the metadata of deposited publications will adhere to the following guidelines:

- The metadata will be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or an equivalent license, following the FAIR principles, particularly focusing on machine-actionable aspects.
- The metadata will include information such as publication details (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue), Horizon Europe funding information, grant project name, acronym, and number, licensing terms, and persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action, their organizations, and the grant.
- If applicable, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for any research output or necessary tools and instruments to validate the conclusions of the publication.

4 Dissemination and communication activities: Awareness Creation

Dissemination is focused on transferring knowledge and depends on the kind of knowledge transferred to the target audience. To enhance the visibility of the project the following ENTRUST dissemination activities will be performed, such as participation in conferences, use of the online media (project website, newsletter, and social media), and meetings/trainings/workshops with relevant stakeholders.

Communication activities are focused on conducting public engagement activities, i.e., events where specialists listen and interact with non-specialists, to ensure that research and innovation activities are made known to the professional as well as the society at large. Also, press releases of the project will be published in local and European media, uploaded on the project's website and spread on social media in order to communicate the results further. Additionally, articles related to the project will be published on European journals and on all partners' social media as well as on the project's website. Finally, the project is going to be presented in various conferences/seminars/events by the partners.

4.1 Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activities Plan

The dissemination activities will deal with the diffusion of research, scientific and technological knowledge generated within the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact by informing the European target audiences. Dissemination activities are characterised by active, a priori awareness and validation by the targeted audiences. They will be collectively performed by all partners, according to each partner's profile and expertise. The for-profit partners will approach relevant industries, as well as their distributors and client networks, while the academic and research partners will focus on disseminating the project results towards research institutes, the technical community, and universities across Europe, which constitute key target audiences. A plan is devised to ensure that a suitable interactive and/ or non-interactive dissemination activity is chosen based on the target audience and presents different intensities depending on the phase and the evolution of the project.

The key objectives of such a plan are included below:

- Provide widespread visibility to the project and its outputs.
- Target key decision-makers who can support the implementation of the project.
- Demonstrate how the outcomes of ENTRUST are relevant to the lives of citizens.

The first phase is defined by raising awareness and engaging with a wide audience, focusing on the key targets and potential stakeholders but truly communicating about the problems that ENTRUST aims to solve and the innovative solution envisioned. This is an important step in getting the message out to the public. This phase involves creating and distributing content that informs people about the context of the project and the problem it aims to solve. The second phase consists of promoting ENTRUST’s scientific and technological developments, its results in addressing the original requirements of its users and its different stakeholders in general or its potential to do so in the long run. This phase is designed to ensure that all stakeholders are kept up to date on the progress of the project. The third phase, (the acceleration to) the exploitation phase aims to increase the visibility and reach of a project’s results with a glance at the outcomes and long-term impact.

Table 10 - Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activities

Target group	Engage	Promote	Exploit
Healthcare providers and organizations, Device Manufacturers, Suppliers	LinkedIn/ Twitter posts, on-page SEO, project announcement letter, blog posts, landing pages, events, newsletters	CTA on LinkedIn, website, newsletters, blog posts, events	Tailored newsletter, project final event, workshops
Cybersecurity & Trusted Computing researchers / engineers, IoT Community	Blog posts, social media posts, project announcement letter, newsletters, workshops	CTA on research articles and social media posts, blog posts, events	Tailored newsletter, project final event, workshops
National & EU Public Authorities, Policy / Decision Makers	Social media posts, project announcement letter, blog posts	CTA links on social media and website, events	Tailored newsletter, project final event, workshops
Patients/ General public	Social media posts, on-page SEO, project announcement letter, blog posts	CTA on the website, links on social media, blog posts	Tailored newsletter, social media campaigns

The consortium will follow a phased approach to defining, planning, organising, and exploiting a rich set of activities and instruments in the most effective way.

Table 11 - Dissemination, Communication and Outreach activities b

Activity Type	Engage	Promote	Exploit
Social Media	Establishment of presence in social media Promote project's outcomes and events; interact with followers to get feedback.	Promote project's outcomes and events. Interact with followers to get feedback answer on comments and private messages on various channels; upload public material; reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags.	Promote project's outcomes and events; interact with followers to get feedback answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; upload public material; reproduce relevant content.
Project Website	Establishment of project's website Creation of the basic sections of the website	Regular update Web analytics monitoring Provide content of impact	Regular update Web analytics monitoring Provide content of impact
Project's Blog	Deploy project's blog provide blog posts related to project's positioning and technologies.	Provide frequent blog posts to initiate discussions on specific issues relevant to the project to receive feedback.	Publish frequent blog posts to demonstrate and promote project's results and/or to promote and attract partnerships and growing user base
Communication Material	Project branding and visual identity, communications starter pack	Prepare revised communications pack and frequent releases of: Newsletter publish blogs/news in EU instruments (e.g. Cordis News, research EU magazines etc.)	Prepare final communications starter pack and frequent releases of Newsletters and videos, publish blogs/news in EU dissemination instruments
Participation in third party events	News items to announce the project's launch, presentations at events and conferences.	News items to announce the significant events/results News items to promote the business case of the project's results.	Promote (new) partnerships. Acknowledge successful collaborations.

4.2 Sustainable Dissemination and Communication Approach

The ENTRUST project is committed to adopting a sustainable approach in its dissemination and communication activities, considering principles of environmental responsibility and resource conservation. To achieve this, the project partners will implement the following practices:

Minimizing Material Resources: ENTRUST aims to reduce the use of material resources wherever possible. This includes avoiding unnecessary printing of flyers and promotional materials and instead promoting online downloads. By embracing digital platforms, the project can minimize paper waste and promote eco-friendly information dissemination. When printing is necessary, partners will opt for recycled materials, ensuring the responsible use of resources. Single-use products will be avoided to reduce environmental impact.

Promoting Sustainable Mobility: The project recognizes the importance of sustainable mobility practices to reduce emissions. ENTRUST will actively encourage participants to choose sustainable transportation options when attending project events, such as recommending bicycle use and promoting the use of public transport. Partners may also implement incentive programs to reward individuals who choose eco-friendly transportation methods. By promoting sustainable mobility, the project aims to reduce carbon footprint and contribute to a greener environment.

Collaboration with Sustainable Suppliers: ENTRUST will prioritize collaboration with suppliers who share the project's commitment to sustainability. Whether it is printers, caterers, or other service providers, the project will seek out partners who utilize sustainable products and materials. By supporting environmentally conscious suppliers, ENTRUST ensures that its dissemination and communication activities align with sustainability principles throughout the entire supply chain.

By adopting these sustainable practices, ENTRUST not only minimizes its environmental impact but also sets an example for other projects and stakeholders in the field of IoT and healthcare. The project's commitment to resource conservation, emissions reduction, and collaboration with sustainable suppliers underscores its dedication to responsible and eco-friendly dissemination and communication efforts. Through these actions, ENTRUST strives to contribute positively to the environment while effectively sharing its mission, progress, and achievements with stakeholders and the wider community.

5 Capacity Building and Contributions to Clusters

ENTRUST places great emphasis on collaboration and recognizes the value of leveraging existing networks and partnerships to maximize the impact of its outcomes. In line with this approach, ENTRUST has identified numerous associations, forums, and clusters where its results and outcomes can be effectively presented and shared.

By engaging with these relevant clusters and associations, ENTRUST aims to foster collaboration, exchange knowledge, and promote the adoption of its research findings and artifacts. The project recognizes the importance of connecting with stakeholders who can directly benefit from ENTRUST's contributions, particularly in the domains of cybersecurity and healthcare. The project's established relationships with community stakeholders, including cybersecurity and healthcare vendors, are instrumental in facilitating the dissemination and implementation of ENTRUST's artifacts. These stakeholders have a vested interest in addressing the existing challenges surrounding the secure implementation of next generation connected medical systems. By leveraging these partnerships, ENTRUST can effectively communicate the value of its solutions and support the industry in addressing the critical need for enhanced security in healthcare IoT.

Through active participation in relevant associations, fora, and clusters, ENTRUST can showcase its outcomes, share best practices, and foster collaborative initiatives. This collaborative approach ensures that the project's research findings reach a broader audience and that its artifacts are adopted and implemented by industry stakeholders. By actively seeking synergies and engaging with relevant clusters and associations, ENTRUST aims to establish a sustainable ecosystem that promotes the secure development and deployment of connected medical systems. By leveraging existing relationships and collaborating with stakeholders who share a common interest in cybersecurity and healthcare, the project can drive meaningful impact and contribute to the advancement of secure healthcare IoT technologies.

In summary, ENTRUST's collaboration strategy encompasses identifying and capitalizing on synergies with relevant associations, forums, and clusters. By leveraging established relationships with cybersecurity and healthcare vendors, ENTRUST aims to share its outcomes, artifacts, and best practices with stakeholders who can directly benefit from and contribute to the project's mission of securing the next generation of connected medical systems. Through collaboration and knowledge exchange, ENTRUST aims to drive positive change and enhance cybersecurity in the healthcare sector.

5.1 Associations, Clusters, Initiatives and Marketplaces

In that context ENTRUST will participate in activities related to several initiatives like AIOTI and IoTSF communities where the focus contributing on the design of lightweight security enablers for the IoT including also medical devices. Actually the main focus is the monitoring of the activities on AIOTI related to the use cases and the architecture WG in order to identify possible impact of the security design. Additionally, ENTRUST will envision to engage some collaboration with existing Marketplaces to be considered would be, among others, FIWARE, and EUROSMART so as to bring the project one step closer to the market and ensure dialogue with potential investors, funders and/or customers. The endmost goal is for ENTRUST to create a working item on guiding cyber-security for medical devices (leveraging approaches such as the IoT Catalogue & Marketplace) for promoting its security solutions to all of the stakeholders comprising the entire healthcare supply chain. A tentative list of possible collaborations is indicated below:

Table 12 - Possible Associations, Clusters, Initiatives and Marketplaces

Cluster/association/fora	Website	Target group	How ENTRUST can contribute?
IoT Forum	iotforum.org	SME, industry, research	Organize sessions at IoT Week and Digital Around the World
Privacy Symposium	privacysymposium.org	Data protection authorities, regulators, industry, research	Organize sessions at the Privacy Symposium conference, Submit research for the Call for Papers
FIWARE	https://www.fiware.org/	Industry	Collaboration on data models
WHO	who.int	Regulator, health sector	Collaboration, information sharing
AIOTI	https://aioti.eu/	SME, industry, research	WG on High Level Architecture for IoT, Edge Computing and Digital Twins and WG on Security and Privacy

5.2 HEU-level associations, clusters, projects and working groups

ENTRUST recognizes the value of engaging with HEU-level associations, clusters, projects, and working groups, particularly those within HEU Cluster 4. The project has actively participated in discussions with various projects to share experiences and explore potential collaborations. As part of these efforts, a workshop was initially planned to take place during the IoTWeek 2023. However, due to unforeseen circumstances, the event has been postponed to 2024, and in the

meantime, a virtual workshop is being organized on June 16th to continue the exchange of knowledge and ideas.

In addition to HEU-level engagements, ENTRUST is also keen on targeting the industrial communities that have significant potential for commercially exploiting the project's results. This includes exploring collaborations with entities like the Industrial IoT Consortium, which can leverage ENTRUST's outcomes to enhance industrial IoT applications and security. While the list of potential collaborations is tentative, ENTRUST has identified promising opportunities for cooperation. These collaborations can lead to mutually beneficial outcomes and support the wider adoption of ENTRUST's research findings and artifacts. By actively engaging with HEU-level associations, clusters, projects, working groups, and industrial communities, ENTRUST aims to foster meaningful partnerships, knowledge exchange, and commercialization of its results. By expanding its network and collaborating with relevant stakeholders, ENTRUST can drive the practical implementation of secure IoT solutions in various sectors. These collaborations will contribute to the project's mission of advancing the field of IoT security and promoting the widespread adoption of secure connected systems.

In summary, ENTRUST's engagement efforts encompass HEU-level associations, clusters, projects, and working groups, along with industrial communities. Through discussions, workshops, and collaborations, the project aims to share experiences, explore potential synergies, and actively involve stakeholders in the development and deployment of secure IoT solutions. The tentative list of collaborations signifies ENTRUST's commitment to forming partnerships that enhance the project's impact and foster the commercial exploitation of its results. Our activities will also target the industrial communities, that hold more potential in commercially exploiting the results (i.e., Industrial IoT Consortium). A tentative list of possible collaborations is indicated below:

Table 13 - Possible HEU-level associations, clusters, projects and working groups

Other Fora	Website	Target group	How ENTRUST can contribute?
ECSO	Error! Hyperlink reference not valid.	SME, industry, research	WG1 on Certification

IIC	https://www.iiconsortium.org/	Industry and stakeholders	to identify the best technology practices in the healthcare sector related to security
Global Semiconductor Alliance	https://www.gsaglobal.org/	Industry and stakeholders	TIES/SWG-03 – Enabling Trusted & Secure IoT Services with Scalable and TIES/SWG-02 – Secure Chip-to-Cloud Solutions for Enablement of IoT Services:
IoXT Alliance	https://es.ioxtalliance.org/	Industry and stakeholders	share insights on cyber-security standards for the healthcare domain especially for operationalizing trust
Trusted Computing Group (TCG)	https://trustedcomputinggroup.org/	SME, industry, research	ENTRUST will push the new breed of AI-assisted attestation enablers

6 Standardization and Regulation Activities, Contribution to Guidelines

Standard Developing Organizations (SDOs) have played an active role in the development and endorsement of numerous standards related to healthcare and the digital transformation, specifically in the context of Connected Medical Devices. Moreover, both within the European Union and beyond, the regulatory landscape imposes various rules on medical device developers that must be considered. Ensuring alignment with relevant standards and applicable regulations is essential to realizing the vision of ENTRUST. Recognizing the significance of standardization, the project has identified it as a key activity for establishing collaborations with appropriate bodies and introducing the project's innovative approach. To effectively address these requirements, ENTRUST will adopt a dual approach to standardization. Firstly, it will conduct an investigation of

existing standards and relevant regulations, compiling a synthesized list that project partners can refer to (in collaboration with T2.1). This will enable the consortium to have a comprehensive understanding of the regulatory landscape and relevant industry standards. Secondly, ENTRUST will establish liaisons with relevant SDOs, capitalizing on the existing relationships within the consortium. Through these liaisons, the project will actively contribute and submit proposals to the appropriate bodies, where appropriate. By engaging with SDOs, ENTRUST aims to influence the development of standards and ensure the incorporation of its innovative approach.

As part of the standardization methodology, MI has distributed a questionnaire among consortium members. This questionnaire serves multiple purposes: validating the importance of regulations and standards, assessing the consortium's involvement with SDOs, and evaluating the standardization potential of ENTRUST. By gathering input from consortium members, the project can ensure that the identified standards and regulations are comprehensive and that the standardization efforts are aligned with the expertise and priorities of the consortium.

Through a proactive and systematic approach to standardization, ENTRUST aims to establish a solid foundation for the implementation of its solutions and ensure compliance with applicable regulations. By engaging with relevant SDOs, the project can contribute to the development of standards that promote the secure and effective use of Connected Medical Devices. This collaborative effort will enhance the project's credibility, facilitate interoperability, and support the broader adoption of ENTRUST's innovative approach across the healthcare sector.

To sum up, ENTRUST recognizes the importance of standardization and alignment with regulations in achieving its vision. The project will investigate existing standards and regulations, establish liaisons with SDOs, and actively contribute to the standardization process. By pursuing standardization, ENTRUST aims to shape the future of healthcare IoT and ensure the successful integration of its solutions within the regulatory framework.

The distributed standardization questionnaire was based on the 3 W principle, as follows:

- **WHAT** are the topics and assets with standardization potential within ENTRUST,
- **WHERE** these could be submitted and with which SDOs ENTRUST should liaise with
- **WHO** can lead and support standardization efforts within the ENTRUST consortium.

All ENTRUST partners have submitted their answers on time. The questionnaire can be found in Annex A. The following two sub-sections will list relevant standards and regulations and will draw

up a Standardization Activity Plan to guide standardization efforts for the duration of the project. It must be noted, however, that the ENTRUST project is still in the early stages of development. Therefore, it would not be feasible to list all possible topics and assets relevant for standardization. Depending on the technical developments of the projects, new assets will likely appear at later stages of the project.

6.1 Global standards and Legislations

6.1.1 Relevant standards

Standards provide guidance on the best practices for managing the risks associated with CMDs. By complying with these standards, ENTRUST can develop a more robust risk management strategy that protects CMDs against cyber threats. They also ensure interoperable, meaning they can work together seamlessly. The ENTRUST project can leverage standards to ensure that its trust management architecture can work with other CMDs, allowing for better integration and coordination between devices.

The following list records the standards that could be relevant to ENTRUST:

- American National Standards Institute (ANSI)
 - ANSI/AAMI 2700 Medical Devices and Medical Systems - Essential Safety And Performance Requirements For Equipment Comprising The Patient-Centric Integrated Clinical Environment (ICE)
 - ANSI/HL7 CDAR2 PHMRPTS R1 Clinical Document Architecture
 - ASTM F 3286 Standard Guide for Cybersecurity And Cyberattack Mitigation
 - ANSI/NEMA HN 1-2019 ANS - Manufacturer Disclosure Statement for Medical Device Security
 - AAMI TIR97:2019 Principles for Medical Device Security - Postmarket Risk Management for Device Manufacturers
- German Institute for Standardization (DIN)
 - EN 14484 Health Informatics - International transfer of personal health data covered by the EU data protection directive - High level security policy.
- Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)
 - IEEE P2817 Guide for Verification of Autonomous Systems
- International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)
 - IEC 62304 Medical Device Software - Software Life Cycle Processes

- IEC 62366-1 and -2; Medical devices- Part 1 and Part 2 Application of usability engineering to medical devices
- IEC 60601-1:2023 SER Series
- Medical electrical equipment
- IEC 60601-2-1:2020 Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-1: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of electron accelerators in the range 1 MeV to 50 MeV
- IEC 80001 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices — Part 1: Safety, effectiveness and security in the implementation and use of connected medical devices or connected health software.
- Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)
 - IETF MUD (RFC 8520) Manufacturer Usage Description Specification
- International Organization for Standardization (ISO)
 - Medical devices
 - ISO 13485 Medical devices — Quality management systems — Requirements for regulatory purposes
 - ISO 14971 Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices
 - Health informatics
 - ISO/TR 27809 Health informatics — Measures for ensuring patient safety of health software.
 - ISO/IEEE 11073-10101 Health informatics — Device interoperability — Part 10101: Point-of-care medical device communication — Nomenclature
 - ISO/IEEE 11073-40101 Health informatics — Device interoperability — Part 40101: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Processes for vulnerability assessment
 - ISO/IEEE 11073-40102 Health informatics — Device interoperability — Part 40102: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Capabilities for mitigation
 - Information technology
 - ISO/IEC 18045 Information security, cybersecurity, and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security — Methodology for IT security evaluation
 - ISO/IEC 15408 Information security, cybersecurity, and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security

- ISO/IEC 30111 Information technology — Security techniques — Vulnerability handling processes
 - ISO/IEC 27039 Information technology — Security techniques — Selection, deployment and operations of intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPS)
 - ISO/IEC TS 30104 Information Technology — Security Techniques — Physical Security Attacks, Mitigation Techniques and Security Requirements
 - ISO/IEC 27001 Information security management systems
 - ISO/IEC 27002 Information security, cybersecurity, and privacy protection — Information security controls
- ISO/TR 22100-5 Safety of machinery — Relationship with ISO 12100 — Part 5: Implications of artificial intelligence machine learning
- International Telecommunications Union (ITU)
 - ITU-T H.812 Interoperability design guidelines for personal connected health systems: Services interface
 - ITU-T X.1205 Overview of cybersecurity
 - ITU-T X.1080 e-Health and world-wide telemedicines - Generic telecommunication protocol
 - ITU-T Y.4117 Requirements and capabilities of the Internet of things for support of wearable devices and related services
 - ITU-T Y.4908 Performance evaluation frameworks of e-health systems in the Internet of things
 - ITU-T E.805 Strategies to establish quality regulatory frameworks.
- Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG)
 - 2019-16 Guidance on Cybersecurity for medical devices
- National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)
 - SP 800-124 Guidelines for Managing the Security of Mobile Devices in the Enterprise
- U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA)
 - UL 2900 Cybersecurity Standard for Medical Devices

6.1.2 Applicable legislation

Applicable regulations ensure that CMDs meet the necessary legal requirements for safety, security, and privacy. Compliance with legislation is essential to protect patients' health data and maintain trust in the healthcare system.

The following list contains regulations that are relevant to ENTRUST:

- International
 - Convention for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (Convention 108 and Convention 108+)
- European Union
 - Directive 98/79/EC (in vitro diagnostic medical devices)
 - Directive 2002/58/EC (ePrivacy Directive)
 - Directive 2005/36/EC (Professional qualifications)
 - Directive 2011/24/EU (Patients' rights in cross-border healthcare)
 - Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS Directive)
 - Directive (EU) 2022/2555 (NIS 2 Directive)
 - Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 (eIDAS)
 - Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation)
 - Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (Medical Device Regulation)
 - Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR)
 - Regulation (EU) 2019/881 (Cybersecurity Act)
 - Regulation (EU) 2022/868 (Data Governance Act)
 - EU cybersecurity framework
- National regulations
 - Normen (NO)
 - Personopplysningsloven (NO) (Personal Data Act)

6.2 Standardization Activity Plan

As previously mentioned, ensuring alignment with existing standards is a crucial step for ENTRUST before engaging in further standardization activities. This approach allows the project to leverage established best practices and identify any gaps that can be addressed through its work. By aligning with existing standards, ENTRUST can build upon a solid foundation and contribute to the advancement of industry standards. ENTRUST's objective in the realm of standardization is to establish and strengthen relationships with Standard Developing

Organizations. This involves actively sharing the research outputs of the project with SDOs and actively participating in their ongoing work items. Through these collaborations, ENTRUST aims to contribute to existing work or introduce new work items that align with its objectives and expertise.

When we refer to contributions in the context of standardization, we encompass various outputs of the project that are shared with SDOs. This includes demonstrations, presentations, tutorials, and active participation in Study Group/Committee meetings. Additionally, ENTRUST may engage in pre-standardization activities, which involve exploring innovative concepts and approaches that have the potential to shape future standards. In some cases, ENTRUST may even contribute to the development of completely new standards that address the unique challenges and requirements of secure Connected Medical Devices. By actively engaging with SDOs and contributing to the standardization process, ENTRUST can have a direct impact on the development of industry standards. This collaborative approach ensures that the project's research outputs are shared with the relevant stakeholders and incorporated into the broader standardization efforts. Furthermore, by actively participating in SDO activities, ENTRUST can influence the direction of future standards, ensuring that they address the specific needs and advancements in the field of healthcare IoT security.

The project recognizes the importance of aligning with existing standards as a precursor to its standardization activities. By establishing or strengthening relationships with SDOs, the project aims to share its research outputs and contribute to their ongoing work. Contributions can take various forms, including demonstrations, presentations, tutorials, active participation in meetings, and even the development of new standards. Through these activities, ENTRUST actively shapes the standardization landscape, ensuring that its innovative solutions and insights are incorporated into industry standards to advance the field of secure Connected Medical Devices.

To monitor the progress and status of prospective contributions, MI will set up a specific excel sheet titled '*ENTRUST Standardization*' with the following fields to be populated:

- What
 - Name of contribution
 - Type of contribution
- Where (name of SDO)
- When (planned submission/actual submission date)
- Who (name of the partners)
- Status

- Comments

6.2.1 Assets for standardization (WHAT)

Based on the results of the distributed questionnaire, the following topics and assets were suggested by the ENTRUST consortium to be considered for standardization:

- Integration of security profiles in certification
- Communication protocols and data formats
- Testing and certification methodologies
- Performance metrics and benchmarks
- Threat detection, and management
- Detection techniques and algorithms
- Trust models
- Risk assessment process
- Real-time conformity certification
- Cybersecurity baseline for medical devices
- Secure data interchange protocols
- Trustworthiness of devices
- Trust assessment framework
- Dynamic trust assessment framework for CMDs
- Direct Anonymous Attestation schemes
- Attribute based Encryption schemes
- Verifiable Credentials schemes
- Swarm Attestation

Based on this, 6 distinct topics can be distinguished:

1. Cybersecurity certification
2. Threat detection
3. Trust assessment framework architecture
4. Risk assessment
5. Secure data and communication protocols
6. Cryptography and encryption

6.2.2 Standards Developing Organizations (WHERE)

Based on the results of the distributed questionnaire, the following Standard Developing Organizations were suggested by the ENTRUST consortium for setting up liaisons and potentially submitting contributions:

- **Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI)**
- **American National Standards Institute (ANSI)**
- **Big Data Value Association (BDVA)**
- **European Committee for Standardization – European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CEN-CENELEC)**
 - CEN-CLC/JTC 13 Cybersecurity and data protection
 - CEN-CLC/TC 62 Electrical equipment in medical practice
 - CEN/CLC/TC 3 Quality management and corresponding general aspects for medical devices
- **European Cyber Security Organization (ECISO)**
- **European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)**
 - ETSI TC Cyber
- **European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)**
 - Cybersecurity Certification (EUCC)
- **Global Semiconductor Alliance (GSA)**
 - TIES/SWG-03 – Enabling Trusted & Secure IoT Services with Scalable
 - TIES/SWG-02 – Secure Chip-to-Cloud Solutions for Enablement of IoT Services
- **Industrial IoT Consortium (IIC)**
- **Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)**
- **International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC)**
 - SC 62A Common aspects of medical equipment, software, and systems
 - SC 62D Particular medical equipment, software, and systems
- **Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)**
 - Operations and Management Area Working Group
- **International Organization for Standardization (ISO)**
 - ISO/IEC JTC1/WG13 Trustworthiness
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC27 WG2 Cryptographic protocols
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 Internet of things and digital twin
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 Artificial intelligence

- ISO/TC 210 Quality management and corresponding general aspects for products with a health purpose including medical devices.
- ISO/TC 215 Health informatics
- **International Telecommunications Union (ITU)**
 - Study Group 11 Protocols, testing & combating counterfeiting.
 - Study Group 17 Security
 - Study Group 20 IoT, smart cities & communities
 - AI for Good
- **IoXT Alliance**
- **Trusted Computing Group (TCG)**

6.2.3 Standardization partners (WHO)

The following table lists the existing standardization activities of the consortium members:

Table 14 - ENTRUST consortium ongoing standardization activities

Partner name	SDO	Working Group/Committee	Topic
UMU	IETF	Operations and Management Area Working Group	Operations and management
	ESCO	Meta schema for certification	Certification process of security properties
SMNS	OSLC	NA	REST APIs
	IHE	NA	Health information
	IEC	TC 57 Power systems management and associated information exchange	Power systems control equipment and systems
		TC 65 Industrial-process measurement, control, and automation	Industrial process measurement
	ISO	NA	NA
	IEEE	NA	NA
	OPC Foundation	NA	NA
	PROFIBUS & PROFINET International (PI)	NA	NA
RA	CEN-CENELEC	JTC13	WG3, 6, 9
	ISO	JTC1/SC27	WG3, 4
	ENISA	EUCC	Cybersecurity certification
		EUCS	Cloud Services Scheme
PARTICLE	CEN	CBRNe SENSOR API	Forensics and crime detection
MI	ECCP	Europrivacy International Board of Experts	Certification Scheme continuous development
	ITU-T	SG11	Protocols, testing & combating counterfeiting

		SG17	Security
		SG20	IoT, smart cities & communities
		FG-TBFxG	Testbed federation
	ISO	JTC 1/SC 42	Artificial intelligence
SURREY	TCG	TPM Working Group and Internet of Things	Internet of Things
	ISO	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG2	Security mechanism
UBI	ISO	ISO/IEC JTC1/WG13	Trustworthiness
	Global Semiconductor Alliance	TIES/SWG-03	Enabling Trusted & Secure IoT Services with Scalable Platforms

The following table identifies the organizational focal points who will lead standardization contribution processes at the specified SDOs:

Table 15 - ENTRUST Standardization focal points

Partner name	Focal point	SDO
UMU	Antonio Skarmeta Sara Matheu Nieves	IETF, ECSO
SMNS	Gabriel Danciu	OSLC, IHE, ISO, IEC, IEEE, OPC Foundation, PI
RA	Roland Atoui	CEN-CENELEC, ISO, ENISA, IIC, loXT Alliance
MI	Sébastien Ziegler Adrian Quesada Rodriguez Renata Radocz	ITU, ISO, IIC, ECCP
SURREY	Liqun Chen	TCG, ISO
UBI	Thanassis Giannetsos	TCG, ISO

On top of this list, most ENTRUST partners have expressed interest in jointly contributing to SDOs and supporting standardization efforts.

6.2.4 ENTRUST Standardization Roadmap

The following table provides a synthesized Standardization Action Plan and Roadmap based on the inputs received.

Table 16 - ENTRUST Standardization Activity Plan

WHAT	WHO		WHERE	
Topic or asset	Related WP	Lead SDO facilitator	SDO	Working Group/Committee
Cybersecurity certification	WP2, WP3, WP4	UMU, RA	ENISA	EUCC
		UMU		ECSO
		MI	ECCP	Europrivacy International Board of Experts

<i>Threat detection</i>	WP2, WP3, WP5	RA	CEN	JTC13
		UMU	IETF	OMA WG
		SMNS	IEEE	IEEE SA
		SMNS, RA, MI, SURREY	ISO	JTC1/SC27 ISO/TC 210
		MI	ITU	SG11, SG17
		RA	IoT Alliance	
<i>Trust assessment framework</i>	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	SURREY	TCG	
		UMU	IETF	OMA WG
		SMNS	IEEE	IEEE SA
		SMNS, RA, MI, SURREY	ISO	JTC1/SC27
		MI	ITU	SG11, SG17, SG20
		RA	IoT Alliance	TCG
		UBI	ISO	ISO/IEC JTC1/WG13
<i>Risk assessment</i>	WP2, WP3	SURREY, UBI	ISO	SC27 WG2
		UMU	IETF	OMA WG
		MI	ITU	SG17
		UMU	IETF	OMA WG
<i>Secure data and communication protocols</i>	WP3, WP5	SMNS, RA, MI, SURREY	ISO	JTC1/SC27 JTC 1/SC 42
		SMNS	IEEE	IEEE SA
		MI	ITU	SG11, SG17, SG20
		RA	CEN	JTC13
<i>Cryptography and encryption</i>	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5	SURREY, UBI	TCG	
		SMNS	IEEE	IEEE SA
		MI	ITU	SG11, SG17
		SMNS, RA, MI, SURREY, UBI	ISO	JTC1/SC27

The following table provides Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the progress and success of the standardization actions carried out in ENTRUST.

Table 17 - Standardization Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Key performance indicator	Target
Number of contributions to standards	3

Number of contributions to SDOs	4
Number of liaisons set up	3
Liaisons with Automotive	3
Liaisons with Transport/mobility	3
Percentage of joint contributions	50%

7 Exploitation Plan

The ENTRUST project's exploitation strategy is a comprehensive approach that combines strategic business planning and marketing analysis to guide the commercialization of key project assets as well as to ensure the long-term sustainability of project's activities and outcomes. This strategy holds significant importance, especially in the face of increased digital risks in the medical industry. The project recognizes the need to address these risks and focuses on leveraging its outcomes, such as assets, algorithms, and tools, to develop innovative applications and services.

The exploitation strategy encompasses both partner-specific and joint approaches, recognizing the diverse expertise and capabilities within the consortium. By utilizing project results, ENTRUST aims to create value by delivering novel solutions that address the security challenges in the medical industry. These solutions may involve the utilization of open-source components as well as IP-protected elements, ensuring compatibility with Open Science principles and fostering collaboration within the broader research community. In addition to leveraging project outcomes, the consortium will explore alternative paths for exploitation. This proactive approach allows ENTRUST to identify new opportunities and potential markets for its solutions. By transitioning project results into market offerings, the project aims to maximize the impact of its research and provide tangible benefits to stakeholders in the healthcare sector.

Trust among partners is a fundamental element of the exploitation strategy. The consortium recognizes that strong collaboration and mutual trust are essential for successful exploitation of project results. The partners will work closely together, sharing knowledge and expertise, to drive the development and commercialization of innovative solutions. Furthermore, ENTRUST acknowledges the importance of participating in standardization working groups. By actively engaging in these groups, the project can contribute to the development of industry standards and ensure that its solutions align with emerging requirements and best practices. This involvement further strengthens the project's positioning within the market and enhances the adoption of its offerings. To reinforce the exploitation strategy, each partner will develop individual exploitation plans tailored to their specific capabilities and market opportunities. These plans will outline the steps and actions required to maximize the commercial potential of the project outcomes. By aligning individual plans with the overall strategy, the consortium can effectively coordinate their efforts and optimize the exploitation of ENTRUST's research outputs.

In a nutshell, the ENTRUST project's exploitation strategy is a comprehensive roadmap that combines strategic planning and marketing analysis. It leverages project assets to create innovative applications and services while addressing the digital risks in the medical industry. The strategy embraces partner-specific and joint approaches, open-source and IP-protected components, and active participation in standardization. By fostering trust among partners and

developing individual exploitation plans, ENTRUST aims to maximize the impact and value of its research outputs, ultimately benefiting the medical industry and society as a whole.

The exploitation strategy of the project encompasses three main paths that will be followed to maximize the impact and value of its research outcomes:

1. Open-source components
2. Individual and joint commercialization of the project's results
3. Long-term sustainability of project's outcomes and new opportunities for additional funding to increase the maturity of the project

This chapter will further describe the means to sustain all of the enumerated directions.

To ensure effective exploitation of its outcomes, the ENTRUST project has developed a sustainable market roadmap, supported by a business model canvas. This roadmap will serve as a guide to navigate the various exploitation mechanisms and maximize the project's impact in the market. In order to protect intellectual property rights, the consortium plans to establish a joint venture for the commercialization of its outcomes, fostering collaboration among partners and providing a unified approach. With the aim of becoming commercialization-ready within three years post-project, ENTRUST recognizes the need for additional funding and collaboration across multiple exploitation paths. This includes seeking external investments and partnerships to support the scaling and deployment of the project's solutions. By leveraging these resources, the consortium can accelerate the market entry and adoption of its innovations, bringing tangible benefits to the healthcare industry.

Furthermore, ENTRUST's exploitation plan goes beyond the exploitation of individual components. The consortium actively explores alternative avenues to maximize the project outcomes. One approach is to offer the solution and risk assessment as a service, enabling organizations to access and benefit from the expertise and tools developed by ENTRUST. Additionally, the consortium considers consultancy roles for organizations lacking in-house expertise to effectively manage cybersecurity issues in the healthcare sector. By providing specialized consulting services, ENTRUST can address the specific needs of these organizations and assist them in enhancing their security measures.

The comprehensive and multi-faceted nature of the exploitation plan ensures flexibility and adaptability in capitalizing on the project results to their fullest potential. By considering a range of exploitation paths, including commercialization, service offerings, and consultancy roles, ENTRUST can cater to various market demands and opportunities. This approach reflects the project's commitment to delivering practical solutions and maximizing the societal impact of its research outcomes.

7.1 Open-Source Roadmap for CMD Trust Reference Implementation

ENTRUST understands that successful open-source projects thrive on active community participation and collaboration. Therefore, the project is committed to fostering a vibrant and engaged community around its open-source platform. ENTRUST aims to establish an open-source platform for the majority of developments contributed by academic partners, hosted primarily on Github (linked to Zenodo community).

Recognizing that open-source practices necessitate a comprehensive understanding and diligent preparation, ENTRUST will undertake work towards:

- the **identification of open-source** trust reference conceptual architecture including both the publication of all technical artefacts (e.g., TEE extensions, attestation enablers, verifiable credentials, runtime verification trust anchors, etc.);
- the contribution of the mechanisms to **the respective standards**;
- the **implementation of an open-source roadmap**;
- **Community Building**: The project will actively reach out to potential contributors, users, and stakeholders to create a diverse and inclusive community around the open-source platform. This includes organizing developer meetups, hackathons, and online forums to facilitate networking, knowledge sharing, and collaboration.
- **Developer Support**: ENTRUST will provide comprehensive support to developers who contribute to the open-source platform. This includes maintaining clear communication channels, offering documentation and tutorials, and establishing mechanisms for feedback and bug reporting. By ensuring a supportive environment, the project can encourage active engagement and continuous improvement of the open-source developments.
- **Collaboration Opportunities**: The project will actively seek collaborations with other open-source projects, both within and outside the healthcare domain. By leveraging synergies and sharing resources, the project aims to foster cross-pollination of ideas and accelerate innovation. Collaboration can take the form of joint development efforts, knowledge exchange, and co-creation of solutions.
- **Continuous Improvement**: ENTRUST recognizes that open-source practices are dynamic and require continuous improvement. The project will actively gather feedback from the community, monitor emerging trends, and adapt its strategies accordingly. This iterative approach ensures that the open-source platform remains relevant, responsive, and aligned with the evolving needs of the community.

By prioritizing community engagement and embracing open-source principles, ENTRUST aims to foster a collaborative and impactful ecosystem around its developments. The project believes that by actively involving the community, it can enhance the quality, adoption, and long-term sustainability of its open-source platform.

The Open-Source Roadmap for CMD Trust Reference Implementation of ENTRUST will focus on the open-source specifications for the secure connected medical devices, generating benefits for the community's stakeholders, such as Academia, Industry and Standardization bodies. A detailed plan will be developed to enable the release of the ENTRUST trustworthiness reference architecture under an open-source scheme. At the same time, a preparation plan will be created for the generation of a minimum viable product (MVP), considering training on open-source engagement, and agreeing on the IPR and licensing approaches. It coordinates the validation of the open-source contributions and foster participation in engagement events, thus, enhancing end-user adoption and the ENTRUST fast deployment.

To ensure the execution of an effective open-source development plan, ENTRUST will adopt the Open-source Development (OSD) plan template, being developed by the OpenContinuum support action. This template is specially curated for collaborative projects, differentiating between in-project activities and post-project exploitation. It promotes partner interactions during plan preparation and execution via internal workshops. The template will encompass:

1. Information on key stakeholders involved
2. Context information illustrating business intentions
3. Strategic information including open-source business canvas, licensing, community approach, and governance.
4. Engagement information detailing stakeholder interaction and activities
5. Project development insights such as environment, development and release approach, support, and evaluation
6. Approval and commitment details.

The open-source roadmap will steer the journey through three successive phases – pre-pilot, pilot, and post-pilot – aligning with the integration of the framework into validated market products, real-life situation validation, and impact assessment and benchmarking.

The Open-Source Roadmap for CMD Trust Reference Implementation of ENTRUST will not be a static document but an evolving strategic tool designed to guide the release of the ENTRUST trustworthiness reference architecture under an open-source scheme.

Figure 14 - Roadmap Components

Identify:

In the identification phase, the foundational building block for the CMD Trust Reference Implementation of ENTRUST will be established. Comprehensive information about key stakeholders will be collected, ensuring their roles, responsibilities, and areas of influence are understood. The business intentions that will underpin the project will be clarified, with core principles, goals, and values to be defined. A strategic overview, including the open-source business canvas, licensing, community approach, and governance, will be developed. Stakeholders' interaction and activities will be taken into account as these will be seen to influence the progress and success of the project. Approval and commitment details from the stakeholders will be secured, ensuring the necessary buy-in to move forward. Throughout the process, alignment with the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and Data Management Plan will be maintained.

Analyse-Select:

In the Analyse-Select phase, the development of an initial Minimum Viable Product (MVP)

Preparation Plan will be initiated. The plan will outline the necessary features, specifications, and resources for building a baseline product that encapsulates the core functionality of the ENTRUST trustworthiness reference architecture. Concurrently, an initial plan for implementing this architecture under an open-source scheme will be formulated. Appropriate open-source licenses, community interaction mechanisms, governance structures, and contribution guidelines will be determined.

Implement:

During the Implementation phase, open-source contributions from community members will be validated and incorporated into the project. This approach ensures that a wide range of perspectives and talents will be harnessed, strengthening the overall quality of the product. Active participation in engagement events will be encouraged. These events, such as workshops, webinars, or online forums, will offer avenues for community members to collaborate, share ideas, and contribute to the project.

Deliver:

In the final Delivery phase, enhancement of end-user adoption and promotion of the fast deployment of ENTRUST will be the main focus. Once the ENTRUST open-source implementation is completed, comprehensive documentation, tutorials, and support resources will be created. This will ensure it is easy for end-users to understand, deploy, and utilize the software. The community will continue to be engaged, ensuring they will be given the necessary resources and support to use ENTRUST effectively. As the rapid deployment of ENTRUST proceeds, performance will be closely monitored, and user feedback will be collected to make necessary improvements and enhancements.

7.2 Focused Target Market

The current landscape of healthcare cyber threats is highly challenging and multi-faceted. As an industry that handles enormous quantities of sensitive data, healthcare organizations have emerged as soft targets for cybercriminals. This is further exacerbated by the fact that these organizations have historically focused more on patient care rather than security, leaving their digital infrastructures vulnerable to cyberattacks.

7.2.1 Current situation

Several factors contribute to this vulnerability, including limited staffing resources, a reliance on outdated and un-patched legacy systems, a lack of security awareness among staff, and the sheer size of the attack surface presented by the diverse range of systems and devices in use.

These factors have led to a surge in cyberattacks against healthcare organizations worldwide. The impact of these attacks is evident from a statistic of 2022, that shows that Healthcare is the most targeted sector in Q2 2022. Notable among these threats are ransomware attacks, where cybercriminals encrypt an organization's data and demand payment in exchange for its release. The widespread and damaging impact of ransomware is also known, this type of attack being the most popular threat incident. Another significant area of vulnerability in the healthcare sector lies in the infrastructure and applications used by healthcare providers. These include firewalls, server applications, cloud storage, web applications, and systems like Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS) used in radiology. These infrastructure elements, if not properly secured, can be exploited by attackers to cause harm or exfiltrate sensitive data. The increasing prevalence of digital medical devices, both implantable and wearable, has also introduced new avenues for cyberattacks. Despite their potential benefits in enhancing patient care, these devices often possess weak authentication mechanisms and access controls, making them easy targets for malicious actors. certain clinical information stations and telemetry servers may introduce risks to patients while they are being monitored. As the healthcare sector continues to grapple with these challenges, compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union and the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) in the United States can help bolster the sector's defensive posture. These regulations impose strict rules around the collection, storage, and processing of personal data, contributing to the overall data security in healthcare organizations.

7.2.2 Target Market

ENTRUST has 4 primary target markets:

1. Medical Device Manufacturers

Manufacturers of medical devices face rigorous regulatory requirements and the need to meet high standards for product safety and effectiveness. With the growing connectivity of medical devices and the associated cybersecurity risks, these challenges become even more complex. However, ENTRUST's Design-time toolbox as well as Trust Management Architecture offers a powerful solution for manufacturers to tackle these issues head-on. By integrating ENTRUST's solutions into the design and development processes of their products, manufacturers can incorporate built-in trust management features. This ensures that their devices have robust security measures in place from the ground up. By prioritizing security and embedding trust management, manufacturers not only enhance the safety of their devices but also strengthen their overall security profile.

The inclusion of ENTRUST's solutions in their products can significantly boost the attractiveness of manufacturers' offerings in a competitive market. As cybersecurity becomes an increasingly vital consideration for healthcare providers and patients, the presence of built-in trust management features sets manufacturers apart from their competitors. Customers are more likely to choose devices that prioritize security, giving manufacturers a competitive edge.

Furthermore, incorporating ENTRUST's solutions reinforces manufacturers' reputation for producing high-quality and safe devices. By demonstrating a commitment to cybersecurity and proactive risk management, manufacturers establish themselves as trusted providers in the industry. This reputation for reliability and security can lead to long-term customer loyalty and positive brand perception.

As the healthcare industry continues to evolve, cybersecurity will remain a critical concern. By leveraging ENTRUST's Trust Management Architecture, manufacturers can address these concerns and stay ahead of regulatory requirements. Additionally, ENTRUST provides ongoing support and updates to help manufacturers stay resilient against emerging threats and maintain compliance with evolving regulations.

The project's Trust Management Architecture empowers manufacturers of medical devices to navigate the complex landscape of cybersecurity risks. By integrating ENTRUST's solutions, manufacturers enhance the security profile of their products, gain a competitive advantage, and reinforce their reputation for quality and safety. Embracing ENTRUST's approach positions manufacturers to succeed in an industry where cybersecurity is increasingly paramount.

2. Cybersecurity Solution Providers

The ENTRUST Trust Management framework not only benefits medical device manufacturers but also serves as a valuable blueprint for cybersecurity solution providers in developing tailored solutions for the healthcare industry. By leveraging the framework and its principles, solution providers can create innovative cybersecurity solutions that address the unique challenges and requirements of the healthcare sector.

The modular and adaptable nature of the ENTRUST framework allows solution providers to apply its principles and components to other industries beyond healthcare. This flexibility enables them to extend their offerings and cater to diverse sectors that require robust cybersecurity measures.

Furthermore, ENTRUST's dual licensing approach provides cybersecurity solution providers with the opportunity to integrate the framework into their existing solutions. By

incorporating the ENTRUST framework, solution providers can enhance the level of security offered to their clients. This integration enables them to leverage the proven trust management features and methodologies of ENTRUST, thereby strengthening their own cybersecurity solutions. By utilizing the ENTRUST framework, cybersecurity solution providers can tap into a well-established and comprehensive approach to security in the healthcare industry. This enables them to provide specialized solutions that align with industry regulations, best practices, and emerging cybersecurity threats specific to healthcare. The adoption of the ENTRUST framework by cybersecurity solution providers not only enhances their offerings but also instils confidence in their clients. The utilization of a trusted and recognized framework demonstrates a commitment to delivering effective cybersecurity solutions tailored to the unique needs of the healthcare industry.

In summary, the ENTRUST Trust Management framework provides cybersecurity solution providers with a blueprint to develop tailored solutions for the healthcare industry. By incorporating the framework into their existing solutions and leveraging its principles, solution providers can offer robust security measures to healthcare organizations. This approach extends their capabilities beyond healthcare and enables them to cater to diverse industries while maintaining a high level of cybersecurity expertise.

3. Healthcare Providers

In the context of the increasing deployment of connected medical devices, the paramount concern is the security of these devices. While these devices have the potential to significantly enhance patient care, healthcare providers require assurance that the devices they use are not only reliable but also safe from cyber threats. The nature of health data, with its sensitivity and value to malicious entities, makes healthcare providers a prime target for cyberattacks. ENTRUST recognizes the criticality of security in healthcare and offers a robust and tested cybersecurity solution to address these concerns. By implementing ENTRUST's cybersecurity solution, healthcare providers can have peace of mind knowing that the transfer and storage of patient data are secure. The solution is designed to ensure compliance with regulations such as GDPR, safeguarding patient privacy and confidentiality. By leveraging ENTRUST's cybersecurity solutions, healthcare providers can effectively mitigate potential security threats and protect their systems and patient data from unauthorized access or breaches. This not only strengthens the overall security posture of the healthcare organization but also instils confidence in patients who entrust their sensitive information to these providers. Furthermore, the implementation of ENTRUST's cybersecurity solutions can have additional advantages for healthcare

providers. It allows them to meet patient expectations regarding data privacy and security, fostering trust and confidence in the healthcare services offered. Patients are increasingly aware of the risks associated with their personal health data and expect healthcare providers to prioritize its protection. By demonstrating a commitment to robust cybersecurity measures, healthcare providers can differentiate themselves in the market and enhance their reputation as trusted custodians of patient information. In summary, ENTRUST's cybersecurity solutions offer healthcare providers the means to address security concerns associated with connected medical devices. By implementing these solutions, healthcare providers can ensure the secure transfer and storage of patient data, comply with regulations, and protect against potential security threats. Moreover, the adoption of ENTRUST's cybersecurity solutions can enhance the reputation and trust of healthcare providers among patients and the wider healthcare community.

4. Regulators and Standardization Bodies

Regulatory bodies play a crucial role in safeguarding patient safety and data security in the rapidly evolving landscape of connected medical devices. To effectively address the challenges posed by emerging technologies, these bodies must continuously refine and update regulations and standards. The ENTRUST framework, with its comprehensive approach to trust management, offers valuable insights and models that can assist regulatory bodies in their efforts. By adopting and adapting the recommendations put forth by ENTRUST, these bodies can enhance the effectiveness of their regulations, ensuring they remain relevant and responsive to the evolving technological landscape.

By leveraging the ENTRUST framework, regulatory bodies can gain a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between cybersecurity, patient safety, and data privacy. The framework provides a structured and holistic approach to addressing these critical aspects, enabling regulators to establish robust and up-to-date guidelines for the development, deployment, and use of connected medical devices.

By incorporating ENTRUST's recommendations into their regulatory frameworks, these bodies can promote the adoption of best practices in the healthcare industry. This, in turn, fosters a culture of cybersecurity and trust among healthcare providers, patients, and the public at large. It ensures that the entire healthcare ecosystem maintains a high standard of cybersecurity, reducing the risks associated with connected medical devices and instilling confidence in the technology's capabilities. Furthermore, the collaboration between regulatory bodies and the ENTRUST project can facilitate knowledge exchange and information sharing. This collaborative approach allows regulators to stay informed

about the latest developments in trust management and cybersecurity, enabling them to adapt their regulations proactively and effectively.

In summary, the ENTRUST framework provides regulatory bodies with valuable insights and models for addressing the challenges of connected medical devices. By adopting and adapting the recommendations, regulatory bodies can enhance the effectiveness of their regulations and standards, promoting a high standard of cybersecurity and trust in the healthcare industry. This collaboration between regulatory bodies and the ENTRUST project contributes to the ongoing improvement of patient safety and data security in the rapidly evolving landscape of connected medical devices.

7.2.3 Business opportunities

With the growing trend of digitization and automation in these industries, cyber risks are only likely to increase. They need sophisticated cybersecurity solutions that can protect their vast and complex digital infrastructure without impeding their operations.

ENTRUST's offerings could include advanced threat detection and response capabilities, encrypted data protection, and secure access management systems. These solutions can ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of critical information, thereby supporting the companies' business continuity and compliance with regulatory standards.

7.2.3.1 Market segments

Healthcare Institutions:

Traditional healthcare institutions, such as hospitals, clinics, and healthcare networks, play a vital role in providing patient care. However, they often face challenges when it comes to managing and mitigating cybersecurity threats effectively. These institutions may lack the necessary resources, expertise, and budget to address the complex and evolving landscape of cybersecurity.

Cost-effectiveness is a significant consideration for healthcare institutions, particularly in the public sector where budget constraints are prevalent. Implementing cybersecurity solutions that are affordable and offer a good return on investment is essential. ENTRUST recognizes the importance of providing cost-effective solutions that meet the specific needs of healthcare institutions, enabling them to allocate their limited resources efficiently.

User-friendliness is another critical factor for healthcare institutions. Implementing cybersecurity measures across various departments, which may have varying levels of technical expertise, requires solutions that are easy to use and understand. ENTRUST places a strong emphasis on

user-friendliness, ensuring that healthcare professionals can adopt and implement the cybersecurity measures seamlessly, without requiring extensive technical knowledge or support.

Compliance with regulations and guidelines is of utmost importance in the healthcare sector, particularly in public sector institutions. ENTRUST understands that healthcare institutions operate within specific regulatory frameworks that govern the handling and protection of sensitive patient information. ENTRUST solutions can be designed to align with these requirements, ensuring that healthcare institutions remain compliant while protecting critical healthcare information and systems.

By addressing these specific needs, ENTRUST can provide healthcare institutions with tailored cybersecurity solutions that are user-friendly, cost-effective, and compliant. Implementing ENTRUST solutions can help healthcare institutions safeguard their critical healthcare information, protect against cyber threats, and maintain the continuity of patient care. By empowering healthcare institutions with robust and accessible cybersecurity measures, ENTRUST contributes to the overall resilience and security of the healthcare sector.

Healthcare Start-ups and Digital Health Companies

Innovative healthcare organizations at the forefront of the industry, leveraging technologies like AI, machine learning, and IoT, face unique cybersecurity challenges. The nature of their operations and the valuable intellectual property they possess make them attractive targets for cyber threats, including corporate espionage and intellectual property theft.

These organizations require robust security measures that can effectively protect their advanced digital infrastructure and innovative solutions. They cannot afford to compromise on the security of their products, services, and proprietary information. ENTRUST's advanced trust management architecture is specifically designed to address these challenges.

By implementing ENTRUST's solutions, these organizations can benefit from a comprehensive and advanced cybersecurity framework. ENTRUST's architecture offers robust security measures that can guard against sophisticated threats and vulnerabilities. It provides advanced encryption, authentication, access control, and monitoring capabilities to safeguard their innovative solutions and protect their sensitive data.

The trust management architecture of ENTRUST ensures that these organizations have a high level of control and visibility over their digital assets, allowing them to mitigate risks effectively. By adopting ENTRUST's solutions, they can bolster their cybersecurity posture, reducing the

potential for cyberattacks, data breaches, and intellectual property theft. This, in turn, helps protect their business continuity, reputation, and overall success.

Furthermore, ENTRUST's solutions are designed to be scalable and adaptable, catering to the evolving needs of innovative healthcare organizations. They can integrate seamlessly into existing infrastructure and workflows, minimizing disruptions and maximizing the efficiency of cybersecurity operations.

By choosing ENTRUST, innovative healthcare organizations can confidently protect their advanced digital infrastructure, maintain the integrity of their products and services, and mitigate the risks associated with cybersecurity threats. ENTRUST's advanced trust management architecture empowers these organizations to focus on their core mission of delivering cutting-edge healthcare solutions, knowing that their cybersecurity is in safe hands.

7.2.3.2 Customer Groups

Healthcare IT Professionals

These organizations operate at the cutting edge of healthcare, often employing innovative technologies such as AI, machine learning, and IoT in their products or services. As such, they may be more open to innovative cybersecurity solutions that can adequately protect their advanced digital infrastructure. They need robust security measures that can guard against sophisticated threats, including corporate espionage, that can lead to the start-up or company failure. ENTRUST's advanced trust management architecture can offer them the level of protection they require, securing their innovative solutions and safeguarding their business.

Healthcare Executives and Decision-makers

This group, including management officials, often controls the budget for cybersecurity measures and plays a crucial role in risk management decisions. For them, clear communication regarding the value and importance of the services is critical. They need to understand the potential risks and the consequences of inadequate security, as well as the return on investment that effective cybersecurity measures can provide. ENTRUST can provide this group with the necessary insights and justification to invest in robust cybersecurity measures.

Medical Staff

Doctors, nurses, technicians, and other medical staff members are often the end users of cybersecurity measures. For this group, ease of use is essential. They need solutions that can integrate seamlessly into their workflows, with friendly interfaces that require minimal technical expertise to operate. In addition, they could benefit from training regarding security, including awareness programs that can help them understand potential threats and how to avoid them. ENTRUST's solutions, with their user-friendly design and comprehensive training programs, can meet these needs effectively.

7.3 Exploitation Roadmap

The Exploitation Roadmap will serve as a strategic guide to aid the consortium in recognizing and organizing initiatives to be carried out post-project. The paramount risk a consortium encounters is the potential failure in executing the exploitation and dissemination plan, or advancing the TRL level or market entry, because of resource scarcity. The Exploitation Roadmap will be crafted to counter this risk, alleviate its effects, and lay the groundwork for increased utilization and a more significant impact.

7.3.1 Exploitation plan

The strategy outlines the methods and approaches that will be used to leverage the project's results to their maximum potential, ensuring sustainable benefits for all stakeholders involved.

The methodology for exploitation was organized into a three-phase procedure, with the goal of aiding partners in establishing the project's exploitation strategy detailed in this document. All partners participated actively in the process and made significant contributions to its implementation, as presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15 – Exploitation methodology and process

An exploitation grid will serve as a comprehensive tool to organize and structure the project's exploitable outcomes and their corresponding exploitation strategies.

The exploitation grid will be constructed to orchestrate a systematic data collection process with the participation of all partners and will be tailored towards the market-focused activities and therefore intended for those partners who are inclined towards this type of exploitation.

The grid will allow for a thorough listing and description of all project outcomes that have potential for exploitation. These would be physical assets, algorithms, tools, knowledge, methodologies, etc. For each listed outcome, a corresponding exploitation strategy will be outlined. This may involve commercialization plans, IP protection, open-source strategies, and more.

The grid will allow for the assignment of roles and responsibilities to various project partners or external stakeholders. This will ensure clear delineation of duties for efficient execution of exploitation strategies.

For outcomes that have commercialization potential, the grid will enable detailed planning of market-oriented activities. This includes target audience identification, revenue generation tactics, cost estimation, and risk assessment.

The grid would help identify potential risks associated with each exploitable outcome and its corresponding exploitation strategy. This will allow for proactive risk mitigation planning.

7.4 Exploitable Assets

The exploitable artifacts describe in Table 20, represent a suite of tools and solutions aimed at enhancing digital security, privacy, and operational efficiency. They collectively offer capabilities ranging from assessing trust and risks in digital ecosystems, providing robust authentication, analyzing code, ensuring compliance with standards and regulations, to facilitating secure data sharing and software updates.

Table 18 - Possible HEU-level associations, clusters, projects and working groups

KER	TRL, M1 vs M36		Exploited by partner	Time to market – post project	Targeted market
Trust Assessment Framework	4	5	UBI, TUE, SNMS	2y	Healthcare, Industry 4.0, CCAM, Logistics, Mobility, Smart Energy, Smart Phones, Telecom
LISTIC Graphbased Cybersecurity & Privacy Risk Assessment	5	8	UBI	1y	IoT Ecosystem comprising of apps with overlapping security & privacy considerations: Industry 4.0, Automotive, Health, Energy
Verifiable Credentials	4	5	SURREY, UPRC	>3y	Healthcare, Electronic Transactions, Blockchain, FinTech, Public Services
Customizable PUF-based TC middleware	4	6	QUBI	3y	Cyber-Physical Systems, IoT, Medical Devices, Quantum Software Dev, Cloud Computing
Cross-Domain Digital Twin	4	5	SINTEF	3y	Healthcare, Telecom, Smart Manufacturing
AI-based Code Analysis & Misbehaviour Detection	3	5	S5	3y	Healthcare Applications, ENTRUST MUDs, Shared Mobility
Automated MD re-certification	3	4	RA	3y	Healthcare Applications, ENTRUST MUDs, Shared Mobility
Extended MUD / Protection Profile Certification & MD Conformity Checking	3	5	UMU	3y	Healthcare Applications, IoT, Medical Devices, Software Development
Fully Qualified Data Sharing and SW Update Service through Blockchain	2	4	S5	2y	Healthcare, IoT, CCAM, Smart Aerospace, Smart Satellite
MDR & EHDS certification criteria extension for Europrivacy	2	4	MI	2y	Healthcare, Medical devices, Software development

Each of these artifacts represents a valuable outcome of the ENTRUST project, contributing to the enhancement of cybersecurity, privacy, and efficiency in digital systems and networks. Recognizing the constantly evolving threat landscape, it is crucial to maintain ongoing communication with partners to ensure that the key exploitable results remain relevant and effective in addressing their specific challenges. This can be achieved through regular engagement, such as meetings, to gather feedback and insights from industry partners and update the artifacts accordingly.

Building a strong open-source community around the ENTRUST project is an effective approach to reduce long-term costs. By fostering collaboration and active participation from a diverse range of stakeholders, the project can benefit from the collective expertise, contributions, and support of the community. This open and collaborative approach encourages the sharing of knowledge, resources, and improvements, leading to continuous enhancement of the artifacts and their applicability in addressing cybersecurity challenges.

To ensure the long-term funding of the project, a dual licensing strategy can be implemented. This strategy allows the industry partners to have the option of using the ENTRUST software under a different license that aligns with their specific requirements and business models. This approach promotes wider adoption of the artifacts by providing flexibility and accommodating different industry needs and preferences. Furthermore, in response to the dynamic nature of the threat landscape, industry partners can benefit from procuring services aimed at integrating new protective measures against emerging threats in the future. This proactive approach allows organizations to stay ahead of evolving cybersecurity challenges and ensure the continuous effectiveness of their security measures. By maintaining regular communication, fostering an open-source community, employing a dual licensing strategy, and offering additional services, the ENTRUST project can ensure the long-term relevance, sustainability, and impact of its artifacts. This collaborative and adaptable approach paves the way for continued innovation, knowledge sharing, and industry-wide adoption of effective cybersecurity solutions.

7.5 Long-term sustainability

Ensuring the long-term sustainability and exploitation of a project's results requires strategic planning and foresight to proactively identify opportunities, anticipate challenges, and adapt to evolving market dynamics and technological advancements. This proactive approach enables the project to maximize the value and impact of its results, effectively navigate potential obstacles, and seize emerging opportunities in the ever-changing landscape of cybersecurity and connected medical devices. The following strategies will be considered to achieve this goal.

7.5.1 Exploitation Strategy

This strategy should outline how the project's results will be commercialized or otherwise exploited. For example, if the project develops a new trust management framework for medical devices, the strategy might involve licensing the technology to device manufacturers or offering it as a service to healthcare organizations. This is a complex process that has the following steps:

- **Understand the market.** The first step to creating an exploitation strategy is to understand the market. This involves identifying who the potential users or buyers of the technology are (such as medical device manufacturers or healthcare organizations)
- **Competitor Analysis.** Understanding the competition in the market is an important step. This includes not only other similar technologies but also alternative solutions to the problem the trust management framework is addressing.
- **Public and research funding.** Ensuring the long-term sustainability and exploitation of a project's results also involves leveraging public and research funding as a key strategy. Public funding sources, such as national grants, research EU programs (Horizon Europe and others), and innovation funds, play a crucial role in supporting the project's research and development activities. The project will actively pursue opportunities to secure public funding by identifying relevant funding programs, understanding their eligibility criteria, and aligning the project's objectives with the funding priorities. This may involve developing grant proposals, engaging with funding agencies, and collaborating with research institutions or academic partners to strengthen the project's case for funding. Research funding can be particularly valuable in advancing the scientific knowledge and technological advancements within the project. Collaborating with research institutions or universities can provide access to additional funding streams, research expertise, and specialized facilities. The project will explore partnerships and joint funding opportunities with these institutions to leverage their resources and maximize the impact of the research outcomes. Furthermore, the project will establish strong relationships with funding bodies and research organizations to stay informed about upcoming funding opportunities, calls for proposals, and policy changes that may affect funding availability. Proactive monitoring of the funding landscape will allow the project to strategically position itself to secure funding and sustain its activities over the long term. It is important to note that public and research funding can provide not only financial resources but also validation and recognition for the project's work. Successfully securing public and research funding demonstrates the project's scientific merit, societal relevance, and potential for innovation. This can enhance the project's reputation, attract additional stakeholders, and open doors

to collaboration and further funding opportunities. By actively pursuing public and research funding, the project can ensure the continuity of its research and development efforts, support the commercialization of its outcomes, and contribute to the broader scientific community's knowledge and advancements in the field of cybersecurity for connected medical devices.

- **Private Funding.** Exploring multiple exploitation pathways to maximize the impact and value of the project's results. This can include commercialization through licensing or spin-off ventures, integration into existing products or services, or providing consultancy and training services based on the project's expertise. In addition to public funding sources, private funding will be explored as a key strategy to ensure the long-term sustainability and exploitation of the project's results. Engaging private investors (angel investors, venture capitals, etc.) and seeking partnerships with industry stakeholders will provide access to additional financial resources, expertise, and market connections. By attracting private funding, the project can secure the necessary resources to support continued research and development, as well as the commercialization and marketing efforts of its innovative solutions. Private funding can also enable the project to expand its reach and impact by entering new markets, forging strategic collaborations, and scaling up its operations. To attract private funding, the project will emphasize its potential for market disruption, competitive advantage, and return on investment. Clear value propositions, robust business plans, and compelling market analyses will be developed to showcase the commercial viability and growth potential of the project's outcomes. Effective communication and engagement with private investors, venture capitalists, and industry partners will be maintained to build trust, demonstrate progress, and secure long-term financial support. Furthermore, exploring diverse funding sources such as angel investors, corporate partnerships, and crowdfunding platforms can provide additional avenues to secure private funding. The project will actively seek out opportunities for collaboration and investment from private entities aligned with its mission and vision, leveraging their resources, networks, and expertise to propel the project forward. By diversifying funding sources and harnessing private funding, the project can enhance its financial stability, increase its agility in responding to market needs, and sustain its efforts in driving impactful solutions in the field of cybersecurity for connected medical devices.
- **Commercialization Paths** The commercialization plans can be:

- **Licensing** In this scenario, each partner that develops a component, would maintain ownership of the technology but would give other companies the right to use it in exchange for licensing fees.
- **Product/Service** The technology developed within ENTRUST could also be used as the basis for a new product or service that could be sold directly to healthcare organizations. This might involve additional development work to turn the technology into a user-friendly product or service.
- **Start-up.** Another option could be to create a start-up company to commercialize the technology. This would likely involve securing venture capital or other funding.

Partnerships: Partnerships play a vital role in the long-term sustainability and exploitation of a project's results. By building strategic partnerships with other companies or organizations, the project can leverage complementary expertise, resources, and networks to maximize the impact and reach of its outcomes. One aspect of partnership is collaboration for development. The project can seek partnerships with technology companies, software developers, or system integrators that have expertise in areas relevant to the project's results. These partnerships can involve joint research and development activities, sharing of knowledge and resources, and co-creation of innovative solutions. By collaborating with industry leaders or specialized organizations, the project can accelerate the development and commercialization of its technologies, ensuring they are market-ready and aligned with industry needs. Partnerships for marketing and sales are also crucial. The project can explore collaborations with companies that have established market presence, distribution channels, and customer networks in the healthcare or cybersecurity domains. These partnerships can facilitate the promotion and adoption of the project's outcomes by tapping into the partners' existing customer base and industry relationships. Joint marketing campaigns, co-branding initiatives, or co-selling arrangements can amplify the visibility and market penetration of the project's solutions, reaching a wider audience and generating commercial interest. In addition, organizing workshops or presenting ENTRUST or its modules at industrial or academic events can serve as a platform for partnership building. These events provide opportunities for networking, knowledge exchange, and showcasing the project's achievements. By engaging with potential partners during workshops or conference sessions, the project can initiate discussions, identify common interests, and explore collaboration opportunities. Such interactions can lead to the establishment of mutually beneficial partnerships that support the project's exploitation strategy. It is important to approach partnership building with a strategic mindset, considering the specific objectives, needs, and potential synergies with potential partners. Building relationships based on shared goals, trust, and mutual benefit is key

to successful partnerships that can drive the long-term sustainability and exploitation of the project's results.

8 Conclusion

This deliverable presented in detail the initial Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Standardization planning of ENTRUST project. More specifically, the ENTRUST Project has placed a strong emphasis on effective communication, dissemination, exploitation, and standardization planning to achieve its key performance indicators (KPIs) and maximize its impact. Through a comprehensive strategy, the project has utilized various channels, including its website, social media platforms, and participation in events, to ensure the widespread dissemination of its findings and engage with relevant stakeholders.

To further extend its reach, ENTRUST has leveraged the power of its project's website and social media platforms such as Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube. Through these channels, the project has actively shared key messages, project updates, and relevant content to a broader audience. By adopting a consistent and strategic approach to social media management, ENTRUST has effectively amplified its online presence and facilitated dialogue and knowledge exchange among stakeholders.

In addition to the online platforms, ENTRUST has recognized the importance of active participation and organization of events. By attending conferences, workshops, and seminars, the project has seized opportunities to showcase its research findings, exchange ideas, and network with experts in the field. These events have not only provided a platform for disseminating project outcomes but also enabled fruitful collaborations and potential partnerships / synergies.

ENTRUST also considers the significance of standardization in the vast area of IoT security for healthcare. By aligning with standardization activities, the project will contribute to international cooperation on cybersecurity for healthcare and fostered the establishment of common guidelines and practices. This commitment to standardization ensures that the project's outcomes and methodologies are widely recognized, facilitating interoperability, and enabling a secure and standardized approach to IoT security in the healthcare domain.

Throughout its planning and execution, ENTRUST will continuously monitor and evaluate its communication, dissemination, exploitation, and standardization efforts to measure their effectiveness and impact. By setting clear KPIs and regularly assessing progress, the project will be able to refine its strategies and optimize its activities to achieve desired outcomes.

In conclusion, the ENTRUST Project demonstrates a comprehensive and strategic approach to communication, dissemination, exploitation, and standardization planning. Through its website, social media engagement, participation in events, and commitment to standardization, the project

has effectively shared its research findings, engaged with stakeholders, and contributed to the advancement of IoT security in the healthcare sector. By consistently monitoring and evaluating its efforts, ENTRUST has ensured that its communication activities align with its goals, ultimately maximizing the project's impact and fostering international collaboration in the field of cybersecurity for healthcare.

9 Annex A - ENTRUST Standardisation engagement questionnaire

ENTRUST Standardisation engagement questionnaire

WP7 Dissemination, Standardization, Exploitation & Impact Creation

Standards play an important role in the ENTRUST vision. For *D7.1 Dissemination, communication & exploitation plan* we will (1) identify relevant standards and regulations to be used for aligning the project vision with, and (2) prepare meaningful contributions to and liaisons with relevant Standard Developing Organisations. To do so, the present questionnaire is aimed towards one representative of each project partner in the ENTRUST ecosystem.

Partner name:

Person of contact name:

Person of contact email:

Section 1: Identification of relevant standards and regulations

Which of the following regulations are relevant for ENTRUST?

GDPR

Convention 108

Cybersecurity Act

Data Governance Act

eIDAS

ePrivacy Directive

NIS Directive

Medical Device Regulation

Do you know any other regulations that could be relevant? If yes, please specify:

Which of the following standards are relevant for ENTRUST?

ANSI AAMI TIR57 Principles For Medical Device Security - Risk Management

ANSI/AAMI 2700 Medical Devices And Medical Systems - Essential Safety And Performance Requirements For Equipment Comprising The Patient-Centric Integrated Clinical Environment (ICE)

ANSI/HL7 CDAR2 PHMRPTS R1 Clinical Document Architecture

ASTM F 3286 Standard Guide For Cybersecurity And Cyberattack Mitigation

IEC 80001 Application of risk management for IT-networks incorporating medical devices — Part 1: Safety, effectiveness and security in the implementation and use of connected medical devices or connected health software

IEEE P2817 Guide for Verification of Autonomous Systems

IETF MUD (RFC 8520) Manufacturer Usage Description Specification

ISO 14971 Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices

ISO 27001 Information security management systems

ISO/TR 22100-5 Safety of machinery — Relationship with ISO 12100 — Part 5: Implications of artificial intelligence machine learning

ISO/TR 27809 Health informatics — Measures for ensuring patient safety of health software
ISO/IEC 18045 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security — Methodology for IT security evaluation
ISO/IEC 15408 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Evaluation criteria for IT security
ISO/IEC 30111 Information technology — Security techniques — Vulnerability handling processes
ISO/IEC 27039 Information technology — Security techniques — Selection, deployment and operations of intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPS)
ISO/IEC TS 30104 Information Technology — Security Techniques — Physical Security Attacks, Mitigation Techniques and Security Requirements
ISO/IEEE 11073-10101 Health informatics — Device interoperability — Part 10101: Point-of-care medical device communication — Nomenclature
ISO/IEEE 11073-40101 Health informatics — Device interoperability — Part 40101: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Processes for vulnerability assessment
ISO/IEEE 11073-40102 Health informatics — Device interoperability — Part 40102: Foundational — Cybersecurity — Capabilities for mitigation
ITU-T H.812 Interoperability design guidelines for personal connected health systems: Services interface
ITU-T Y.4117 Requirements and capabilities of the Internet of things for support of wearable devices and related services
ITU-T Y.4908 Performance evaluation frameworks of e-health systems in the Internet of things
ITU-T X.1080 e-Health and world-wide telemedicines - Generic telecommunication protocol
ITU-T E.805 Strategies to establish quality regulatory frameworks.
ITU-T X.1205 Overview of cybersecurity
MDCG 2019-16 Guidance on Cybersecurity for medical devices
NIST SP 800-124 Guidelines for Managing the Security of Mobile Devices in the Enterprise
DIN EN 14484 Health Informatics - International Transfer Of Personal Health Data Covered By The EU Data Protection Directive - High Level Security Policy
UL 2900 Cybersecurity Standard for Medical Devices

Do you know any other standards that could be relevant? If yes, please specify:

Section 2: Liaison with SDOs and contribution to standardisation

What is, according to you, the value proposition of ENTRUST?

What are the key elements (i.e., standardisable assets, research outputs, knowledge) that the project should push to standardisation?

Key element (standardisable asset, research output, knowledge):

Name of SDO or specific standard

Kind of standardisation (i.e., standard data model, standard protocol, best practice, etc.)

Which Standards Developing Organisation should ENTRUST focus on? Please provide as many details as possible:

Name of SDO

Working Group/Study Group/Committee, etc.

Relevant information (i.e., link, description)

Is your organisation a member of a Standards Developing Organisation? If yes, please specify:

Name of the SDO:

Working Group/Study Group/Committee, etc.

Standard development process name and relevant information (i.e., links, description)

Is your organisation directly involved in any standard development processes? If yes, please specify:

Name of SDO:

Standard development process:

Relevant information:

Is your organisation interested in leading standardisation contributions?

Is your organisation interested in making joint contributions with another ENTRUST partner(s)?

Please identify the main contact person at your organisation for standardisation related activities:

Do you have any comments?

10 Annex B – ENTRUST OSD Plan Template

1		Open-source plan info
Authors name and e-mail	<i>REWIRE persons in charge of providing and maintaining the plan. Can involve different partners.</i>	
History	<i>The open-source plan can be updated several times, depending on how the status of its execution. Examples are:</i>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change of strategy - Change in licencing approach - Change in community approach - Change in infrastructure use (e.g. Gitlab to Github) 	
	Date	
	Version	
	Description of modification	
Confidentiality	<i>You may wish to have up to three versions of the plan:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Confidential at partner level (not provided to consortium) – However experience shows that it does not run - Confidential at consortium and EC level (needed for deliverable) - Public (needed for engagement) 	
2		Context
Initial Key exploitation result name	<i>Mention if you have modified your plans with respect to the grant agreement.</i>	
Initial description	<i>Mention if you have modified your plans with respect to the grant agreement.</i>	
Key exploitation result name		
Description	<i>Provide a rationale for the change if you have modified your plans</i>	
Category of building block	<i>How do you position your key exploitation results with respect to the 12 building blocks (OpenDei design principles for data spaces?)</i>	

Figure 16 - OSD Plan Template Part 1

3	Strategy	
3.1	Business	
Open source canvas	<p>Option 1: Major open-source initiative Provide a first version of the open-source canvas. https://opensource.com/article/16/12/open-source-canvas</p> <p>Option 2: Leveraged service business model</p> <p>Option 3: Technology specialist</p> <p>Option 4 Open source foundation</p> <p>Option 5 Co-creation of open-source extendible platforms</p> <p>Option 6 e-Pure service business model</p>	
Assessment within project	Describe tasks to be carried out on business within the project	
Assessment beyond project	Describe tasks that will be carried out on business beyond the project, make recommendations for a roadmap	
3.2	Open-source licensing and IPR	
Current licensing and IPR status	<p>Explain the current status (e.g., the selected licensing plan) and the dependencies. See https://opensource.org/licenses Describe decisions to be made on licensing and IPR within the project</p>	
Analysis	Provide an analysis of how you plan to enforce business-friendly licenses	
Decisions within project	Describe decisions to be made on licensing and IPR within the project, justify when you do not select a well-accepted licensing scheme	
Decisions beyond project	Describe decisions to be made on licensing and IPR beyond the project, justify when you do not select a well-accepted licensing scheme	
3.3	Community Approach	
Community	Assess the intended community approach. Some references	
	<p>(https://opensource.org/community, https://en.wikiversity.org/wiki/Open_community_approach,</p> <p>https://www.linuxfoundation.org/resources/open-source-guides/participating-in-open-source-communities,</p> <p>https://www.eclipse.org/collaborations/)</p>	
	Example of community:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Governance: single organisation, Development: single organisation - Governance: single organisation, Development: community - Governance: open-source organisation, Development: community 	
	Current status of	TRL
KER	Community	
status at the end of	TRL	
	Community	
status beyond	TRL	
	Community	
Decisions within project	Describe decisions to be made on community approach within the project	
Decisions beyond project	Describe decisions to be made on community approach beyond the project	
3.4	Governance	
Governance	<p>Select the agreed open-source governance approach (see https://opensource.com/article/20/5/open-source-governance)</p>	
Decisions within project	Describe decisions to be made on community approach within the project	
Decisions beyond project	Describe decisions to be made on community approach beyond the project	

Figure 17 - OSD Plan Template Part 2

4	Engagement	
4.1	Stakeholders	
Developers	Current team	List developers and their roles. Is the team involving several partners?
	Team evolution during project	Explain if the team will evolve during project
	Team evolution beyond project	Explain if the team will expand externally beyond the project, and how engagement will take place
Users	Intended users	List users (pilots) and their needs
	External users during project	Explain if there will be external users during project, and how they will be engaged
Other stakeholders	List potential stakeholders that can have an interest to the project and need to be engaged - Other open-source communities - Platform / data space stakeholders - Domain specific stakeholders (Consumers, local communities, data energy cooperatives) - Energy and non-energy business stakeholders (finance, healthcare, water, mobility, etc.) - Regulated operators - Standardisation bodies	
4.2	Activities	
Activities within project	Inbound activities: liaison with other projects (through OpenContinuum, and other Horizon projects), presentation to data space events (IoT, BDVA, BRIDGE, ...), conferences, blogs, ... Outbound activities: if any	
Activities beyond project	Inbound activities Outbound activities	

Figure 18 - OSD Plan Template Part 3

5	Project Development
5.1	Environment
Platform	<i>List platforms and dependencies on other products or components</i>
Development environment	<i>Explain development environment used to develop open-source project</i>
Decisions during project	<i>Describe decisions to be made on environment during project</i>
Decisions beyond project	<i>Describe decisions to be made on environment beyond project</i>
5.2	Development and release approach
Development lifecycle	<i>Explain lifecycle approach (development, verification et validation) and approach (e.g. DevOps) including tools to be used</i>
Development lifecycle security assurance	<i>Explain measures for development lifecycle security assurance</i>
Release building approach	<i>Explain approach including tools to be used</i>
Decisions during project	<i>Describe decisions to be made on development and release during project</i>
Decisions beyond project	<i>Describe decisions to be made on development and release beyond project</i>
5.3	Support
Pilots involved	
Contact points pilot	
Contact points KER	
Training material	
Training schedule	
5.4	Evaluation
Schedule	<i>Provide schedule for questionnaire to pilots, questionnaire to developers and evaluation report</i>
6	Evaluation and approval of a plan
Project manager name	
Approval date	
Exploitation manager name	
Approval date	

Figure 19 - OSD Plan Template Part 4

